

**UNIVERSITÀ
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Department of Life Sciences and Systems Biology

Degree of M.Sc. in Industrial Biotechnology

Optimization of a protocol for soil analysis through mass spectrometry-based proteomics and taxonomic and functional analysis of microbial communities to assess soil health status

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Thesis projects carried out through an Erasmus
traineeship project in the
Institute of Microbiology at the
University of Greifswald (GER)

UNIVERSITÄT GREIFSWALD
Wissen lockt. Seit 1456

Academic year 2023/2024

This thesis has been made publicly available via Zenodo, an open access repository for scientific research. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15296740](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15296740)

Table of contents

List of abbreviations.....	5
1. Summary.....	6
2. Introduction.....	8
2.1 Biological community in soils.....	8
2.2 Microbial Communities in soils.....	9
2.3 Impact of agriculture on soils and soil microbial communities.....	11
2.4 Occurrence of antibiotic resistances in soils.....	12
2.5 Metaproteomics as a tool to analyze the composition of microbial communities.....	14
2.6 Aims of this work.....	16
3. Materials and methods.....	17
3.1 Chemicals.....	17
3.2 Consumables.....	18
3.3 Instruments.....	19
3.4 Software, tools, databases.....	21
3.5 Fields overview.....	22
3.6 Experimental design.....	23
3.7 Protocol A.....	24
3.8 Protocol B.....	27
3.9 Protocol B 2.0.....	30
3.10 Protocol C.....	31
3.11 ZIP TIP purification.....	34
3.12 Mass Spectrometry and following data analysis.....	36
3.13 Upset plots.....	39

4. Results	40
4.1 Comparison of protein extraction protocols.....	40
4.2 Metaproteome analysis comparison of extraction protocols B and B2 using the standard 100 minutes LC-gradient.....	42
4.3 Upset plots using the standard 100 minutes LC-gradient.....	43
4.4 Differences between taxonomic composition using the standard 100 minutes LC-gradient.....	46
4.5 Metaproteome analysis comparison of extraction protocols B and B2 using a 180 minutes LC-gradient.....	48
4.6 Upset plots using a 180 minutes LC-gradient.....	49
4.7 Differences between taxonomic composition using a 180 minutes LC- gradient.....	52
4.8 Metaproteomic analysis of peat samples.....	54
4.9 Differences between taxonomic composition using peat samples.....	55
4.10 ARGs detection in soil samples.....	57
4.10.1 Antibiotic resistances using normal gradient.....	57
4.10.2 Antibiotic resistances using long gradient.....	58
5. Discussions	60
5.1 Evaluation of the most performing protocol.....	60
5.2 Taxonomic evaluation of data.....	62
5.3 Analysis of the microbial community composition in peat soils.....	66
5.4 Antibiotic Resistances mechanisms detected in agricultural.....	67
6. Outlook	68
7. References	69
8. List of figures	77

9.	List of tables.....	78
10.	Acknowledgements.....	79
11.	Supplementary material.....	80

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long form
°C	Degrees Celsius
A. bidest.	Bidistilled water
A. dest.	Distilled water
ACN	Acetonitrile
ARG	Antibiotic resistance genes
CAA	2-Chloroacetamide
Da	Dalton
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
FA	Formic acid
FASP	Filter Aided Sample Preparation
g	Gram
h	Hour
H ₂ O-MS	Water in Mass Spectrometry Quality
kDa	Kilo Dalton
l	litre
LC-MS	Liquid Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry
M	Molar
m/s	Meters per second (speed)
m/z	Mass-to-charge ratio
min	Minutes
ml	Millilitre
mM	Millimolar
MS	Mass Spectrometry
MS-MS	Tandem Mass Spectrometry
ppm	Points per million
PVPP	Poly(Vinylpolypyrrolidone)
rpm	Rounds per minute
RT	Room Temperature
SDS	Sodium dodecyl sulphate
sec	Seconds
Tab.	Table
TCA	Trichloroacetic acid
TCEP	Tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine hydrochloride
TEAB	Tetraethylammonium bromide
Tris	Tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane
UT buffer	Urea and Thio-urea buffer
x g	Multiple of the gravitational acceleration relative to the magnitude of Earth's gravity
µg	Microgram
µl	Microlitre
µM	Micromolar

1 Summary

In recent years, it has been increasingly evident that the biological and microbial community in soils are markers for understanding the soil health and quality. Indeed, it was confirmed that the type of crop, as well as the type of treatment of the soil, as well as the type of fertilization used, deeply influences the composition of the microbial community of the soil. Particularly dangerous for the public health, is the presence of ARGs (antibiotic resistance genes) some of which are the result of natural evolutionary biological processes, often due to spontaneous gene mutations or gene transfer. Most, however, are man-made coming from wastewater, intensive livestock farms or places where antibiotics are produced. Having said that, the main goal of this study was to test different published protein extraction protocols that would allow to reliably, accurately, and in a short time frame to analyse the microbial communities in soils from agricultural origin.

In this study, six different soil samples, coming from different farms around Greifswald - the exact location of which is unknown for privacy reasons - were investigated using three different protein extraction protocols and a variant of one of them, in order to find a reliable, reproducible and efficient protocol. During the study, high variations in number of proteins were detected among the different protocols. At the end of this stage, the two best protocols in term of number of identified protein groups (B and B2) were further analysed, using a longer gradient LC-MS, to study whether the quality of the spectra obtained would improve. After the information obtained using normal and longer gradient, the data were further submitted to a series of bioinformatic analyses, in order to have an overview of what is really contained in the soil samples under study. But, given the thousands of proteins detected and the amount of data obtained, and as this is a master's thesis project, mainly focused on finding a suitable protocol for protein extraction from soils (that can be exploited by other researchers/students afterwards), only one taxonomic analysis was carried out on the identified phyla and one functional analysis concerning antibiotic resistance.

The final results showed a very similar composition in phyla among the samples, both in different protocols and in different samples. A peat sample was also analysed, doing two replications and using B and B2 protocols, which confirmed the type of result and reproducibility between the protocols. Instead, the functional analysis, regarding the

antibiotic resistances, showed that the main ARGs are conserved between samples, but their relative abundance can differ greatly between different samples, and in some cases, even between the same sample, using two different protocols, these results, basically, further confirmed that ARGs and resistance-associated proteins are widespread throughout the environment.

Further investigations might reveal more differences about the taxonomy and the ARGs composition among the samples and, of course, among B and B2 protocols, indeed, even if they gave excellent results, they could always be improved.

2 Introduction

The physical and chemical components of soil quality are well understood, and quantification methods for these components exist that are accessible to growers and consultants. Soil biological traits and their relationships with crops are more complex, and there are large deficiencies in fundamental knowledge (Lehman *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1 Soil organisms grouped by class, showing the size of body width (Brackin *et al.*, 2017)

2.1 Biological community in soils

As a whole, the soil biological community provides a number of essential ecosystem services, particularly (Brackin *et al.*, 2017):

- **decomposition of organic matter**, indeed soil organisms macerate and decompose plant and animal residue that is, likely, the most important function of the soil biological community
- **soil formation**: soil microorganisms produce polysaccharide glues that shape soil structure and form aggregates. Networks of fungal hyphae bind mineral and organic particles together, helping to form macro-aggregates. And the larger soil fauna act as 'engineers', by moving or ingesting soil, or creating mounds, casts and burrows.
- **release of nutrients for plant uptake**: many soil organisms impact directly on plant nutrition. For example, many bacteria are involved in nitrogen cycling; arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi promote the crops' uptake of phosphorus and other nutrients; siderophore-producing bacteria chelate iron and other bound nutrients to increase the

availability for plants; and certain fungi and bacteria solubilise phosphates, making them available to plants.

- **storage and recycling of nutrients:** when organic matter is decomposed, complex organic molecules are broken down and eventually reduced to smaller organic substances. During this process, some nutrients are immobilised (i.e. incorporated into living cells). This process governs the supply of nutrients to plants and nutrient equilibrium levels in soil are governed by the soil biota.

- **growth promotion and suppression of pests and diseases:** Rhizosphere inhabitants produce plant growth-promoting substances and endophytic microorganisms that induce resistance to pathogens.

- **degradation of toxins:** Soil organisms produce enzymes that break down pesticides, pollutants and other contaminants.

But certain organism groups are responsible for negative soil biological function, including crop diseases. The fact that stressed or challenged plants secrete a number of molecules which act as signalling compounds between plants and microorganisms also becomes relevant in this respect. Particularly, soil microorganisms are known to use these chemical-based messages, in order to communicate with plants, and by sensing these molecules, they contribute to activate defence mechanisms in the plant under stressed conditions (Glick, 2012).

2.2 Microbial Communities in soils

Soil microbial communities, despite their small size, play several essential roles in maintaining soil fertility and health. Here are the main functions:

- Microorganisms contribute to the decomposition of organic matter and the transformation of elements into forms that plants can absorb.

For example, bacteria from the *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrobacter* participate in the nitrogen cycle by converting ammonium into nitrites and then into nitrates; or mycorrhizal fungi help plants absorb phosphorus.

- bacteria and fungi in the soil break down plant and animal residues, returning essential elements to the soil.

e.g. Fungi from the *Trichoderma* genus or bacteria from the *Bacillus* genus decompose lignin and cellulose in plant residue.

- Some microorganisms release substances that stimulate plant growth or increase nutrient availability.

e.g. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* produces siderophores, which bind iron and make it more available to plants, or *Azospirillum* fixes atmospheric nitrogen and promotes root growth.

- Some microorganisms compete with soil pathogens or produce antimicrobial substances.

e.g. *Bacillus subtilis* produces natural antibiotics against fungal pathogens.

- microorganisms produce substances that improve soil particle aggregation, influencing porosity and water retention.

e.g. Mycorrhizal fungi release glomalin, a protein that contributes to soil aggregate stability or some bacteria secrete polysaccharides that enhance soil particle cohesion.

- Certain microorganisms degrade pollutants and toxic substances, helping to remediate contaminated soils.

e.g. *Pseudomonas putida* can degrade petroleum-derived hydrocarbons or *Rhizobium* and *Bradyrhizobium* assist in the removal of toxic organic compounds.

These functions make the soil microbial community essential for maintaining soil fertility and the health of terrestrial ecosystems.

In addition to their beneficial functions, some soil microorganisms can have negative effects on plants, other organisms and soil quality.

Despite an estimated 5 million species of soil fungi, only around 100,000 have been identified, and just 4,500 species of soil bacteria have been documented out of an estimated 1 billion inhabiting the soil (Nielsen et al., 2016). These gaps in knowledge pose a challenge to developing effective tools for practitioners and advancing our understanding of soil biological properties.

Notably, the vast array of soil organisms, each with unique functions, requirements, and life cycles, continuously interact, shaping the complexity of soil ecosystems.

2.3 Impact of agriculture on soils and soil microbial communities

Substantial evidence exists that agricultural land is usual to select different microbial communities rather than those that develop in soils under native vegetation (Brackin *et al.*, 2013; Jesus *et al.*, 2009; Nourbakhsh 2007).

Reasons include:

- Plant litter inputs are reduced and less diverse in agricultural than natural systems;
- Tillage negatively impacts on fungal hyphal networks and the larger soil fauna (which takes a long time to re-establish);
- Nutrients are supplied separately to carbon as mineral fertilisers rather than bound together in organic materials as occurs in natural ecosystems; and
- Many soil microbes are well adapted to decomposing organic materials; however, their populations tend to decline with reduced substrate availability in agricultural systems.

Instead, intensive monoculture systems tend to promote pathogenic soil microbes that specialise in infecting a narrow range of host crops (Shipton 1977).

Tillage has been recognized as the most important driving factor in influencing soil microbial community in general and bacterial diversity in particular (Dong *et al.*, 2017). Different tillage practices are known to influence soil organic carbon, moisture, and physical properties by and large. Since soil enzyme activity is greatly influenced by these parameters, the type of tillage practice has a direct impact on soil enzyme activities (Bielinska *et al.*, 2012). Intensive tillage and application of chemical inputs in higher rates have widely been exploited in conventional agriculture with the aim to increase production to meet the growing food demands of an ever-increasing human population. As a result, soil binding capacity decreased to considerable extents and agriculture fields became more prone to erosion by surface run-off, which led to non-point sources of pollution across the world (Davis & Fox., 2009).

The increase in the production of certain plants through the addition of fertilizers results in reduction of plant biodiversity in the treated area. The reduction in plant biodiversity, due to addition of fertilizer also results in reduction of the biodiversity of the soil microbiota (Dickson & Gros., 2013; Suding *et al.*, 2015).

Herbicides are chemical molecules designed to reduce the growth of unwanted plants, and thus, they promote the productivity of the plants used in agriculture. Herbicides normally have different weed targets (García-Delgado et al., 2019) and have a high oxidative potential due to the high number of electronegative residues in their structure, including chlorine, phosphoric acid, hydroxide, oxygen, sulfonyl, amines, etc. This increased oxidative potential and other molecular interactions also affect non-target organisms, including other photosynthetic organisms, shredders, primary and secondary predators, and decomposers, including various soil microorganisms, resulting in a general increase in members of the Actinobacteria phylum and other herbicide-tolerant bacteria (Wang et al., 2017). In addition, microbial communities are enriched with microorganisms with the metabolic machinery to degrade and consume such chemicals (Gallego et al., 2019). Agriculture also makes use of other chemical molecules to kill fungi, nematodes, insects, and rodents that affect food production. Again, such molecules alter the biodiversity of the area in which they are used and have a particularly profound effect on soil microorganisms (Mulla et al. 2020; Pingali., 2012).

2.4 Occurrence of antibiotic resistances in soils

Antibiotics were first discovered in the 1920s and are widely used to fight bacterial diseases because of their killing or immunosuppressive effects on pathogens (Olesen et al., 2018). Antibiotics are used, not only to treat various infectious diseases, but also to ensure medical safety. However, the long-term use of antibiotics can make a large number of disease-causing bacteria resistant to antibiotics, which poses a serious threat to human public health safety, and because the large-scale unregulated use of antibiotics generates important selection pressure for drug-resistant bacteria, making the bacteria in the environment resistant or even multi-drug resistant, causing a series of environmental problems (Zhou et al., 2013; Zhi et al., 2019). Although the enrichment of resistance genes in soil has been explored in recent years, there are still some key questions to be addressed regarding the variation of ARG composition in soil with different fertilization treatments, such as the core ARGs in soil after different fertilization treatments, the correlation between ARGs and bacterial taxa. (Wang et al., 2023).

The main use of antibiotics as drugs to treat infections caused by pathogens is to protect human health and promote the healthy development of animal husbandry (Lillenberg et al., 2010), but excessive use is not only not absorbed and utilized by humans and farm animals, but also excreted out of the body with manure and eventually into the environment. Due to the slow absorption and low degradation rate of antibiotics in animals, only 10% can be absorbed and utilized, and most of the antibiotics used in excess will be excreted in their original form or metabolites through urine or feces, and then enter the water, soil and air, causing environmental pollution (Karci and Balcioglu, 2009; Zhang et al., 2015). Moreover, antibiotics in the environment can put stronger selection pressure on indigenous microorganisms, leading to the development of antibiotic resistance (Xu et al., 2022).

Antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) are genetic elements carried by microorganisms that cause them to develop resistance to target antibiotics (Fu et al., 2022). They are persistent and are the source of bacterial drug resistance. After the death of microbial strains carrying ARGs, the DNA carrying ARGs is released into the environment and persists for a long time under the protection of deoxyribonuclease (DNase). But DNA containing ARGs can also be transmitted via Horizontal Gene transfer between live bacteria (transformation, conjugation) or via bacteriophages (transduction). Eventually, this exposed DNA in the environment can be transferred into other microbial strains at the genetic level (Hill and Top, 1998). ARGs are difficult to eliminate once they are produced, and even if antibiotic selective pressure disappears, ARGs will still persist in microbial populations (Crecchio et al., 2005). While soil is considered as a huge reservoir of ARGs in the natural environment, human activities, such as irrigation with reclaimed water and manure application, have greatly increased the antibiotic resistance of soil (Salyers and Amábile-Cuevas, 1997; Mustafa and Scholz, 2011), but soil antibiotic residues accumulate day by day due to irrigation with antibiotic-containing wastewater and continuous input of livestock manure as organic fertilizer to farmland (Yang et al., 2017). During vegetable cultivation, large amounts of animal manure are also applied to improve soil fertility and yield. Numerous studies have shown that application of organic fertilizers significantly increased the abundance and quantity of ARGs and their subtypes in the soil, compared to the non-fertilized soil. The conventional fertilizer application also showed significant enrichment of ARGs, which

indicated that manure addition often had a more decisive effect on ARGs in soil than chemical fertilizers (Wang et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2018; Apreja et al., 2022).

2.5 Metaproteomics as a tool to analyze the composition of microbial communities

Microbial soil communities can be analysed using various techniques that provide insights into their diversity, composition, and functions. Here are some of the main methods:

- The analysis of 16S rRNA (16S) genes has become a fundamental tool for microbial ecologists to assess the microbial composition of various environments, including soils, oceans, and the human body. Due to the high sequence conservation of 16S genes across diverse bacteria, this method enables phylogenetic analysis of microbial diversity and the identification of novel taxa (Haas et al.,2011).
- Metagenomics allows the study of microbial communities directly from environmental samples through the analysis of their genetic material, bypassing the need to isolate and cultivate individual microorganisms. This approach provides a comprehensive picture of taxonomic diversity, the structure of microbial populations and their functional potential.
- The Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) technique is a molecular method commonly used for the identification and analysis of fungal community diversity. It is based on sequencing the Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region of ribosomal DNA (rDNA), which is highly variable between fungal species and therefore ideal for fungal phylogeny and taxonomy
- Metaproteomics, also referred to as community proteomics or environmental proteomics, is highly complementary to other techniques within the field of microbial ecology by providing functional information that can be linked to species/population information.

A metaproteomic analysis of the same sample identifies actually translated genes, revealing important metabolic information of the microbial community (Herbst et al.,2016). Protein extraction methods have to be optimized for each type of sample (Bennford et al., 2009) to cope with interfering substances such as humic acids or

dominating plant proteins, to ensure complete cell lysis or prevent protein loss due to binding to matrix particles. It became clear that changes in these protocols directly influence the recoverable community metaproteomes (Jensen., 1992), (Leary et al., 2014). This is precisely why different extraction protocols were systematically compared in this study to see which was the best.

A point in metaproteomics that needs to be emphasised, is that the absence of protein identification does not prove absence of a protein. Similarly, the identification of a protein does not infer its activity under the detected conditions. At the same time, identification and abundance will likely correlate with its importance in the examined environment (Herbst et al.,2016).

There are many critical points in proteomics that could interfere with the final results, starting with sample collection and storage. For example, care should be taken to avoid contaminating samples with keratins from skin and hair, which add noise to MS datasets. Another critical point is cellular lysis: cells are lysed via chemical (detergents or chaotropic agents); solvent (alcohols or phenol); mechanical (bead-milling, sonication, pressure, grinding, or blending); thermal (snap-freezing or boiling); and/or enzymatic methods (lysozyme, zymolyase, lysostaphin). Most protocols incorporate chemical or solvent treatment with mechanical and/or thermal lysis. Whatever the case, the lysis buffer chosen should inhibit enzymatic and proteolytic activity. This is usually achieved via the inclusion of EDTA and protease inhibitors, such as phenylmethylsulphonyl fluoride or a commercially available inhibitor cocktail (Nebauer et al., 2024). Protein extraction methods should be tailored to suit the sample; hence, there is no one-size-fits-all protocol, for example several are proposed in this study. Moreover, total protein extraction and LC–MS/MS identification are often hindered by bio- or non-biogenic environmental constituents. This has been well-documented in soil studies (Keiblinger et al., 2012; Keiblinger et al., 2016). Briefly, soil organic matter (SOM), which includes the exudates of metabolically active plants and microorganisms and humic compounds formed through the decomposition of plant and animal remains, tends to co-extract and bind with protein. These SOM complexes often manifest as brown streaks on 1D and 2D polyacrylamide gels, which can mask bands and interfere with resolution. Certainly, they may also interfere with protein quantitation assays and MS spectral acquisition (Waibel et al., 2023). That is the reason why filter-aided sample preparation (FASP) has been pursued very often to reduce the loss of proteins in humic

complexes by digesting the protein-humic sample directly, then precipitating humus and undigested protein by acidification (see protocol A, protocol B and protocol B 2.0). Peptides remain in solution and are extracted by centrifugation as they pass through the molecular weight cut-off filter (5–30 kDa exclusion size) (Qian & Hettich, 2017).

Talking about protein identification, the most suitable method in complex samples is a bottom-up approach, which requires protein enzymatic digestion into peptides. Various commercial proteases are available for this purpose. Increasingly common is the use of multiple proteases (e.g., trypsin and LysC), which increases the pool of detectable peptides and can improve the reliability and reproducibility of protein identifications (Saveliev et al., 2013). The most used protease in metaproteomic studies is trypsin. Trypsin is a serine protease that cleaves proteins at the carboxyl side of arginine and lysine residues, with high specificity, into peptides roughly 6–50 amino acids in length, the majority of which will be in the typical mass range required for detection by a mass spectrometer (500–1500 Da). Further, the C-terminal basic residues arginine and lysine provided by tryptic cleavage, optimize the subsequent detection of peptide fragments originating from opposite peptide ends (Nebauer et al., 2024).

Broadly, there are five approaches to peptide generation in a metaproteomic study: in-solution, gel-based (see Protocol A), on-filter, suspension trapping (S-Trap), and single-pot. All approaches require protein reduction and alkylation.

2.6 Aims of this work

Regarding the aim of this work, the most important target is to find an optimised extraction protocol to analyse and study the microbial community of the selected soils, in particular, how much they are affected by the type of crop and by the type of fertilization; basically the health of the soils analysed. To best achieve this goal, it was necessary to develop an efficient protein extraction protocol, that allows to achieve higher quality in tandem mass spectrometry analysis. Subsequently, the spectra obtained, were subjected to a bioinformatic analysis, using several tools and software. The final outcome was a taxonomic and functional analysis of what the starting samples contained. The last step was to look in the literature to correlate the identified species with soil health and quality.

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Chemicals

SUBSTANCE	COMPANY
2-Chloroacetamide	Sigma-Aldrich (St.Louis, USA)
Acetone ROTIPURAN® p.a., ACS, ISO	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Ammonium Bicarbonate	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, GER)
Bromphenol Blue sodium salt	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, GER)
Calcium chloride dihydrate	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt)
Coomassie Brilliant blue G 250	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, GER)
Ethylendiamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA)	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Formic Acid ROTIPURAN® 98% p.a., ACS	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Glycerin ROTIPURAN® ≥99,5%, p.a.	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Guanidine hydrochloride	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Magnesium chloride hexahydrate	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
MS distilled water	General Laboratory supplies
N,N,N',N'-Tetramethyl ethylenediamine (Temed)	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, GER)
Poly(vinylpolypyrrolidone) ~110nm particle size	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, GER)
Porcine modified trypsin 20 mg	PROMEGA (Madison, USA)
Sodium Chloride	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Sodium hydroxide	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Thiourea	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, GER)
Trichloroacetic acid 99%, p.a.	Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, GER)
Triethylammonium bicarbonate buffer (TEAB)	Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, GER)

Tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine hydrochloride powder (TCEP)	Sigma-Aldrich (St.Louis, USA)
Urea	Merck KGaA (Darmstadt)

Table 1: list of substances used during the study

3.2 Consumables

CONSUMABLES	COMPANY
0.1ml Mirco-Insert fo Vials	VWR international (Radnor, Pennsylvania)
Cell Disruption Media 0.1mm glass beads	Scientific Industries (Bohemia, USA)
Centrifugation tubes 15 ml	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht,Germany)
Centrifugation tubes 50 ml	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht,Germany)
Glass vials	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht,Germany)
Micro tube 2ml, PP	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht,Germany)
Microcon® Centrifugal Filters Merck (30kDa)	Merck Millipore Ltd (Cork, IRL)
Pierce™ C-18 Tips	Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, USA)
Pipettes	Gilson (Middleton, USA)
Reaction tubes 1,5 ml	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht,Germany)

Reaction tubes 2 ml	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht, Germany)
Serological pipette 10ml	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht, Germany)
Serological pipette 25ml	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht, Germany)
Serological pipette 5ml	SARSTEDT AG & Co. KG (Nümbrecht, Germany)
VWR Centrifugal filter 10 kDa	VWR international (Radnor, Pennsylvania)

Table 2: list of consumables used during the study

3.3 Instruments

INSTRUMENT	COMPANY
-20°C freezer	Liebherr (Bulle, CH)
4°C refrigerator	Liebherr (Bulle, CH)
-80°C freezer	Liebherr (Bulle, CH)
accu-jet® pro	BRAND GmbH & Co. KG (Wertheim, GER)
Advanced Magnetic Hotplate Stirrers	VWR international (Radnor, Pennsylvania)
Analytical balance	OHAUS Europe GmbH (Nänikon Switzerland)
Concentrator plus	Eppendorf (Hamburg, GER)
EASY-nLC 1200	Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, USA)

FastPrep-24™ 5G	MP biomedical (Irvine, California, USA)
FiveEasy pH meter	METTLER TOLEDO (Columbus, USA)
Glass bottles	General Laboratory supplies
Heraus Megafuge 8R centrifuge	Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, USA)
Hood System DELTA 30	Wesemann GmbH (Basel, CH)
Incubator INCU-Line®	VWR international (Radnor, Pennsylvania)
Knife	General Laboratory supplies
Magnetic Hotplate stirrer	VWR international (Radnor, Pennsylvania)
Magnets	General Laboratory supplies
Nutator	Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG (Schwabach, Germany)
PowerPac™ HC Power Supply	Bio-Rad Laboratories (Hercules, USA)
Q Exactive HF	Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, USA)
qbd4 digital block heater	Grant Instruments Ltd (Cambridge, UK)
Scissors	General Laboratory supplies
spatulas	VWR international (Radnor, Pennsylvania)
TermoMixer® C	Eppendorf (Hamburg, GER)
Touch Screen Dry Bath/Block Heater	Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, USA)
Tweezers	VWR international (Radnor, Pennsylvania)
Ultrasonic bath	Findel International (Hyde, UK)
Vortex-Genie 2	Scientific Industries (Bohemia, USA)

Table 3: list of instruments used during the study

3.4 Software, Tools, Databases

SOFTWARE	COMPANY
Adobe Reader	Adobe Systems
Biorender.com	Biorender
JupyterLab (v 4.3.4)	Project Jupyter
Mascot	Matrix Science
Microsoft office	Microsoft corporation
Prophane	Prophane.de
Scaffold 5	Proteome Software, Inc.

Table 4: informatic tools used during the study

3.5 Fields overview

All agricultural fields are located around the city of Greifswald, Germany. Samples were taken in frame of the AgriBiom Project (funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research) from these sites, transported on ice to the Institute of Microbiology of the University of Greifswald. Soil samples were cleaned of roots and stones, crushed and subsequently freeze dried using a dryer lyophiliser and homogenized using a mixer mill (25 mm ball).

Table 5: information on the treatment of the soils under study over the past three years

	2021/2022			2022/2023			2023/2024		
sample	crop	yield	Fertilizer/ pesticides	crop	yield	Fertilizer/ pesticides	crop	yield	Fertilizer/ pesticides
FF3R1	winter barley	78 dt	mineral, conventional	winter rape	29 dt	mineral, conventional	NA	NA	NA
GF2R1	winter barley	86 dt	mineral, conventional	winter rape	38.4 dt	mineral, conventional	winter wheat	NA	NA
BF2R3	winter wheat	82.6 dt	mineral, conventional	winter rape	36.7 dt	mineral, conventional	Sugar beet	NA	NA
EF3R2	winter rye	45 dt	cow dung, cow manure	corn	200 dt	Chalk, cow manure	Winter triticale	NA	NA
AStR2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
FStiIR2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

The peat sample was collected in June 2021 in the valley of the river Trebel, Mecklenburg/Eastern Pommerania, Germany. The peat sample was treated as described above for the agricultural soil samples.

3.6 Experimental Design

The selected soil samples were chosen to represent diversity in soil composition and environmental influences. These soils were collected from local fields and farms.

Sampling of soil and sediment is typically undertaken using a sediment corer or grab sampler. Visual inspection of the collected sample is important to confirm sample integrity. Collected samples should be homogenized by sifting, which also removes stones and larger debris. Homogenized samples should be stored at $-70/-80$ °C to halt proteolytic and metabolic activities, prior to protein extraction.

Figure 2: metaproteomic analysis scheme, own graphic created in Biorender.com

For the mass spectrometric investigation, the samples must be properly prepared. In particular, after using the three different extraction solutions for each protocol, the following digestion was performed in two different ways: for protocol A and B, Filter Aided Sample Preparation was used, while in protocol C, the digestion was performed through an SDS-page followed by in-gel digestion. After the subsequent desalting, a mass spectrometric investigation followed by database search and investigation was performed, focusing on taxonomic and functional analysis.

3.7 Protocol A: “direct soil protein extraction method” (according to Qian and Hettich, 2017; Wiśniewski, 2017; Chourey et al.,2010)

First of all, 2 ml microtubes with 0,5 ml of glass beads inside each one were prepared, after that 500 mg of freeze-dried and homogenized of 6 soil samples (FF3R1; GF2R1; BF2R3; EF3R2; AstR2; FstilR2) were weighed, adding them directly in microtubes with glass beads.

Then, 1 ml of SDS lysis buffer was added in each tube and all the three components were mixed by hand through shaking slightly.

Afterwards microbial cells were lysed using the FASTPrep-24 5G (5 times X 1min X 5,5m/s) putting the samples in ice between cycles to avoid the possible denaturation of the samples.

Thus, two centrifugations, at 10000g X 10min X 20°C, were made to then transfer the supernatant into 2ml reaction tube (each time).

Then, about 10% of the amount of the supernatant in NaCl was added in each centrifugation tube (for a final concentration of NaCl 100 mM).

This was followed by adding pure acetone to a final concentration of 80%.

Afterwards, the centrifugation tubes were vortexed briefly and incubated for 1 hour at room temperature.

Since the acetone would make the pellet very sticky if centrifuged directly in the centrifugation tube, the transfer of the solution (total amount ~ 3ml) was carried out in two steps inside 2ml reaction tube to then do the centrifugation at 21000g X 20min X 20°C; the supernatant was discarded each time.

Following the centrifugation, 3X Acetone washing was done: the pellets were washed with 1ml of 80% acetone, re-suspended briefly, and centrifuged at 21000g X 10min X 20°C. The supernatant obtained, was discarded each time.

Thereupon, the proteins were air-dried, keeping the reaction tubes open and put in incubation for 5 minutes at 37°C.

At the end the pellet was put in fridge at 4°C overnight.

The following day, the Urea buffer and UT buffer was thawed at RT and the pellet was taken from the fridge; after that, each pellet was topped up with 120µL of SDS lysis buffer to then be incubated for 5 minutes at 95°C for dissolving the protein pellets.

800µL of Urea buffer were added to the dissolved pellets.

Thereafter using the Filter Aided Sample Preparation (FASP) (Wiśniewski, 2017) the samples were reduced and alkylated adding in sequence, in each reaction tube, 37 μ L of 1M CAA and 7 μ L of 1M TCEP to then be gently mixed and incubated for 30 minutes at 30°C. Thereafter the samples were transferred to Merck Microcon 30k for centrifuging at 14000rpm X 20min X 20°C and discarding the respective eluate (since the Microcon has a volume of about 500 μ L the solution was added in two steps and centrifuged until the whole solution was filtered). Then 100 μ L of UT buffer was added to the filters and centrifuged at 14000rpm X 20°C (about 10 min), followed by two washing steps with 100 μ L of Urea buffer and two more washing steps with 100 μ L of 50mM TEAB. In the last TEAB washing step it's essential to centrifuge until the filter is completely dried, then the Microcon tubes with eluate were discarded and new tubes were taken. Finally, to each filter, 95 μ L of CaCl₂ buffer and 5 μ L of trypsin solution was added (for a total of 1 μ g of trypsin). Lastly, the tubes were incubated for 18h at 37°C. The following day, the samples were centrifuged for 10min always at 14000rpm X 20°C. Afterwards, 50 μ L of TEAB was added to each filter and centrifuged for 15-20 min (until the filter had completely dried). Afterwards, the filter was discarded and the eluate was kept, which was dried in the vacuum centrifuge (for about 2h). Thereafter, the peptides were resolved in 100 μ L of 1% formic acid solution. Finally, the desalting was done using the "Ziptip procedure" (Sharma et al., 2012). At the end of the desalting, the samples, ready for MS, were stored in a freezer until measurement.

Table 6: solution used for the protein extraction according to Protocol A

Buffer	Concentration	Components	Handling
SDS lysis buffer	100mM 4% w/v	Tris-HCl SDS	pH 7.6
Acetone	99,8%		Store at room temperature
NaCl	0,5M	NaCl A.Bidest	

UT buffer	8M 2M	Urea Thio-urea	store at -20°C
Urea buffer	2M Stock 8M	Tris-HCl Urea	pH 8.5 and stored at -20°C
TCEP solution	10mM 8M	TCEP Urea buffer	Prepare freshly
CAA solution	40mM 8M	CAA Urea buffer	Prepare freshly
CaCl ₂ buffer	50mM 10mM	TEAB CaCl ₂	Prepare right before use
Trypsin solution (1 μg of trypsin in 5 μL of acetic acid and 95 μL of CaCl ₂ buffer)	20μg 50mM 95%	Trypsin Acetic acid CaCl ₂ buffer	Prepare right before use
Re-suspending solution	1%	Formic acid H ₂ O-MS	Prepare right before use

3.8 Protocol B: “SDS-TCA soil protein extraction method + removal of humic substances” (according to Chourey et al., 2010; Chourey et al., 2018; Wiśniewski, 2017)

Firstly, 2ml- microtubes containing 0,5 ml of glass beads inside was prepared, after that 500 mg of the same samples, used for the protocol A, were weighed (FF3R1; GF2R1; BF2R3; EF3R2; AstR2; FstilR2) adding them directly in microtubes with glass beads. Then, 1 ml of Alkaline-SDS extraction buffer (Abram F., 2014) was added in each tube and all the three components were mixed by shaking by hand. In particular, SDS disrupts the phospholipids in cellular membrane, thus lysing the cells.

Afterwards, for a homogenous and contamination-free lysis the FASTPrep-24 5G was used 5 times X 1 min X 5,5m/s putting the samples in ice between cycles to avoid the possible denaturation of the samples.

Then, two centrifugations at 10000g X 10min X 20°C were done, to then transfer the supernatant into 2ml reaction tubes.

Thereafter, 100% TCA solution was added to a final concentration of 25%, this last step guaranteed the selective precipitation of proteins.

Table 7: table that shows the supernatant left for each sample and the correspondent amount of TCA added afterwards

Samples	Supernatant (µl)	TCA solution (µl)
FF3R1	500	170
GF2R1	500	170
BF2R3	550	185
EF3R2	600	200
Astr2	650	220
FstilR2	650	220

Finally, tubes were capped and gently mixed by inverting them few times. After that, the tubes were kept in a freezer overnight (10-12 h) to precipitate the proteins.

The following day, a centrifugation of the samples at 21000g X 20min X 4°C was done and the supernatant discarded (Bastida et al., 2009).

Afterwards, 3X Acetone washing steps were necessary: in particular the pellet was washed with 1ml of chilled acetone, then centrifuged at 21000g X 10min X 4°C and, at the end, the supernatant was discarded (Becher et al., 2013). This step is important because it removes detergent and soluble contaminants prior to air drying.

Thereupon, the protein pellets had to be Air-dried by keeping the reaction tubes open and putting them in incubation for 5 minutes at 37°C. (Ogunseitán, 2006)

Then the protein pellets were dissolved in 1 ml of guanidine buffer and incubated at 60°C for 1h with intermittent vortexing every 10-15 minutes to denature and to reduce the proteins, thus enhancing the cellular lysis. (Chourey et al., 2010) (meanwhile Urea buffer and UT buffer, that were already prepared, were thawed at room temperature).

Next, for each reaction tube, 100mg of Polyvinylpolypyrrolidone (PVPP) was added and the solution was gently mixed by keeping it on a nutator for at least 5 min.

This step is fundamental because PVPP allows to remove soil debris or humics from the solution making it clearer, ensuring a more accurate analysis in the mass spectrometer.

Then the samples were centrifuged twice at 20800g X 10min X 20°C and the supernatant was collected into a new reaction tube.

Thereafter, using the Filter Aided Sample Preparation (FASP) (Wiśniewski, 2017) the samples were reduced and alkylated, adding in sequence, 28 µL of 1M CAA and 7 µL of 1M TCEP to each reaction tube, and incubated for 30 minutes at 30°C.

After this step, the approach was transferred to Merck Microcon 30k, centrifuging at 10000rpm X 15min X 20°C and discarding the eluate (since the Microcon has a volume of about 500µL, the solution was added in two step and centrifuged until all of the solution was filtered). Afterwards 100µL of UT buffer was added to the filters and centrifuged for a while at 14000rpm X 20°C (about 10 min), then washed twice with 100µL of Urea buffer and centrifuged for a while, and twice with 100µL of 50mM TEAB. As for Protocol A, in the last TEAB washing step, it's essential to centrifuge until the filter is completely dried. At the end of this washing series, the Microcon tubes with eluate were discarded and new tubes were taken. Finally, 95µL of CaCl₂ buffer and 5µL of trypsin solution (for a total of 1mg of trypsin) was added to each filter and incubated for 18h at 37°C.

The day after, the filters with the trypsin solution were centrifuged for 10min at 14000rpm X 20°C. Then, 50 µL of TEAB was added to each filter that was centrifuged

for 15-20 min (until the filter was completely dried).

Afterwards, the filters were discarded, and the eluate was kept; eluate that was dried in the vacuum centrifuge (about 2h).

Thereafter, the samples were adjusted, adding 100 μ L of 1% formic acid solution.

Finally, the desalting was done, using the “Ziptip procedure” (Sharma et al., 2012)

After desalting the samples, ready for MS, they were stored in freezer until measurement.

Table 8: solution used for the protein extraction according to Protocol B (and B2)

Buffer	Concentration	Components	Handling
Alkaline-SDS Extraction buffer	50mM 5% w/v 0,15M 0,1M 1mM	Tris-HCl SDS NaCl EDTA MgCl ₂	pH 8.5
Acetone	99,8%		Store at 4°C
Guanidine Buffer	6M	Guanidine-HCl CaCl ₂ buffer	Prepare directly before use
UT buffer	8M 2M	Urea Thio-urea	store at -20°C
Urea buffer	2M Stock 8M	Tris-HCl Urea	pH 8.5 and stored at -20°C
TCEP solution	10mM 8M	TCEP Urea buffer	Prepare freshly
CAA solution	40mM 8M	CAA Urea buffer	Prepare freshly
TEAB	50mM	TEAB H ₂ O-MS	
Tris-CaCl ₂ buffer	50mM 10mM	Tris-Hcl CaCl ₂	pH 7.6

CaCl ₂ buffer	50mM 10mM	TEAB CaCl ₂	Prepare right before use
Trypsin solution	20µg 50mM 95%	Trypsin Acetic acid CaCl ₂ buffer	Prepare right before use
Re-suspending solution	1%	Formic acid H ₂ O-MS	Prepare right before use

3.9 Protocol B 2.0

As mentioned in chapter 2.3, since modifications of these protocols directly affect the metaproteomes of the recoverable communities, and since protocol B appeared to be the best of the three initially chosen, in terms of the quality of the mass spectrum, for analysing the proteomics of the samples under study, we adopted minor changes in this protocol to see if there was a margin of improvement.

In this variant, the use of PVPP is unnecessary, reason why being, after the steps of dissolving the protein pellet in 1 ml of guanidine buffer, followed by an incubation for 1 hour with intermittent vortexing. The next step is to immediately reduce and alkylate with TCEP and CAA. In addition, the samples, after being adjusted with 100 µL of 1% formic acid, and before being desalted using Zip Tip protocol, they are transferred to VWR 10 kDa centrifugal filters, for cold centrifugation at 4°C X 4500g X 30 minutes. The resulting eluate is used for the Zip Tip protocol. This added step has the task of retaining humic compounds, which would otherwise interfere with the analysis, giving us unreliable results.

3.10 Protocol C: “post-alkaline protein extraction protocol” (according to Herruzo-Ruiz et al., 2021)

After having weighed 500 mg of the usual six samples (FF3R1; GF2R1; BF2R3; EF3R2; AstR2; FstilR2), they were put in 2ml reaction tubes, and the extraction solution in concentration 1:3, so 1,5ml of 0,5M NaOH in 500 mg of sample was immediately added. Afterwards, the reaction tubes were incubated for 15 minutes, inverting gently every 5 minutes.

Then, done in series:

- centrifugation at 500xg X 1 min X 20°C to then transfer the supernatant to a new tube,
- sonication in a sonication bath for 1min,
- one another centrifugation at 500xg, 1min, 20°C to then transfer the supernatant to a new tube, and
- finally, a centrifugation at 25000g X 10 min X 20°C to remove the supernatant

After that, four washes were done: firstly by re-suspending the pellet in 1,5 ml of washing solution (50mM Tris-HCl, pH 7,5, 10% glycerol added before use); secondly by doing 1 minute of sonication; thirdly centrifuging at 25000xg for ten minutes at RT and finally removing the supernatant.

Thereafter, the final pellets were put in freezer at -20°C overnight.

The following day, the pellets were topped up with 30 µL of Laemmli treatment buffer, followed by 5 minutes of boiling at 96°C and by 1 minute of sonication.

Thereafter, the microbial proteins extracted from 500mg of freeze-dried soil in Laemmli buffer have been loaded on SDS-page gels and were run at 150 Volt for 15-20 minutes. Subsequently, the gel was stained, incubating it overnight into a nutator, using a Comassie solution provided by the working group.

The following morning, the gel with the six samples was washed several times with distilled water until the water no longer changed colour. Then, on a sterile glass surface the gel bands were separated and cut with a cutter in cubes of about 1mm³.

After the cubes, belonging to the 6 samples were put in six different reaction tubes and destained with 200 µL of ACN plus 200 µL of Ammonium Bicarbonate 100mM; this step was followed by a centrifugation at 800rpm X 25°C X 30min; at the end, the supernatant

was discarded. The next step was to dehydrate the gel cubes, adding 200 μ L of ACN, and discarding it after 3 minutes.

The cubes were further reduced and alkylated, adding to each reaction tube, 200 μ L of a prepared freshly solution made of: 2 ml of 50 mM TEAB, 80 μ L of 1M CAA and 20 μ L of 1M TCEP, to then be incubated at 70°C for 5 min, and at the end, the supernatants were discarded.

Afterwards, 1ml of NH_4HCO_3 was added in each reaction tube, and the solution was centrifuged at 800rpm X 23°C X 15min, for then discarding the supernatant.

Thereupon, gel pieces needed to be dehydrate with 200 μ L of ACN for each reaction tube, which were dried using a vacuum centrifuge for about 30 min.

Lastly, 50 μ L of trypsin solution (for a total of 1 μ g of trypsin) and 150 μ L of 100mM Ammonium Bicarbonate were added to each sample and incubated overnight at 37°C. The next day, gel pieces were incubated consecutively with 3 solutions: 250 μ L 0,1% TFA 50% ACN; 250 μ L 100mM NH_4HCO_3 ; 250 μ L 100% ACN at 800rpm X 15min X 25°C. In particular, after every incubation, the supernatans were removed and combined after every incubation and, eventually, the resulting supernatant was dried using a vacuum centrifuge.

Thereupon, each dried reaction tube was resuspended with 100 μ L of the re-suspending solution.

Finally, the desalting was done, using the “Ziptip procedure” (Sharma et al., 2012) At the end of the desalting, the samples, ready for MS, were stored in a freezer until measurement.

Table 9: solution used for the protein extraction according to Protocol C

Buffer	Concentration	Components	Handling
Extraction solution	0,5M	NaOH H ₂ O-MS	
Washing solution	50mM 10%	Tris-HCl Glycerol	pH 7.5 add glycerol right before use

Laemmli treatment buffer	0,25mM 8% 40% 0,004%	Tris-HCl pH 6.8 SDS Glycerol Bromophenol blue	Store at -20°C
Ammonium bicarbonate	100mM 50%	Ammonium bicarbonate in H ₂ O-MS Acetonitrile	
TCEP and CAA solution	10mM 40mM 50mM	TCEP CAA TEAB	Prepare freshly
TEAB	50mM	TEAB H ₂ O-MS	
Tris-CaCl ₂ buffer	50mM 10mM	Tris-Hcl CaCl ₂	pH 7.6
Trypsin solution	20µg 100mM	Trypsin Ammonium bicarbonate	Prepare right before use
Re-suspending solution	3% 0,01%	Acetonitrile Acetic acid	Prepare right before use

3.11 Zip Tip purification

A ZipTip® pipette tip is a pipette tip with a micro-volume bed of chromatography medium fixed at its end. It is designed for purifying and concentrating femtomoles to picomoles of proteins and peptides, providing improved data quality. Particularly, the ZipTip reversed-phase (C18) pipette tips contain a silica resin for the concentration of peptides and removal of salts prior to mass spectrometry. It is crucial throughout the procedure to depress and release the plunger slowly to ensure optimal movement of solution through the resin bed, and also care must be taken to avoid the generation of air bubbles during pipetting. Before starting with the procedure, the necessary solutions (table 10) and the apposite glass vials with the glass inserts were prepared. The first step involves the wetting solution: indeed 100 µL of the solution was pipetted and then the supernatant was discarded. This step was repeated twice. After that, also 100 µL of the equilibration solution was pipetted and discarded twice.

The third step concerns peptide binding, in which the re-suspending solutions with peptides (100 µL of 1% formic acid in case of protocol A, B and 0,01% of acetic acid and 3% of acetonitrile in case of protocol C) were pipetted up and down 10-20 times before being pipetted back into reaction tubes. This step was followed by the washing step, pipetting 100 µL of washing solution five times, and discarding the supernatant each time. The final step was to pipet the elution solution (100 µL) 5 times up and down, to then pipet the supernatant directly into glass vial. At the end, all the glass vials were dried in the vacuum centrifuge and stored at -20°C.

They will be topped up with 10 µL of buffer A (0,1% acetic acid in H₂O-MS), shortly before the mass spectrometric analysis.

Table 10: Solution used for Zip-Tip desalting

Solution	Concentration	Components
Buffer A	99,9% 0,1%	H ₂ O-MS Acetic acid
Buffer B	99,9% 0,1%	Acetonitrile Acetic acid

Wetting solution	70%	Buffer B
	30%	Buffer A
Equilibration solution	97%	Buffer A
	3%	Buffer B
Washing solution	100%	Buffer A
Elution solution	60%	Buffer B
	40%	Buffer A

3.12 Mass Spectrometry and following data analysis

In order to understand which of the three protocols are the best in extraction, and in order to assign the extracted peptides to the right proteins and so to the right organism to which they belong, mass spectrometry was performed. Particularly, a tandem mass spectrometry was executed because for the analysis of specific organic compounds in complex mixtures, sensitivity and specificity for target compounds can be achieved with high and nearly instantaneous response (McLafferty, 1981).

LC-MS/MS analyses were carried out on an EASYnLC1200, directly coupled to a Q Exactive HF mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA). Peptides were loaded onto a self-packed analytical column with an integrated emitter (3 μm C18 particles; 20 cm), using buffer A (0.1 % acetic acid) at a flow rate of 2 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. Separation of peptides was achieved by applying an 85 min binary gradient of 4 % to 50 % buffer B (0.1 % acetic acid in acetonitrile) and a flow rate of 300 nL/min. Basically, HPLC ensures that peptides are separated, according to their hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity, before being analysed by the spectrometer. All samples were measured in parallel mode; survey scans were recorded in the Orbitrap with a resolution of 60,000 with m/z of 333-1650. In particular, the 15 most intense peaks per scan cycle were selected for fragmentation. Also, dynamic exclusion of precursor ions was enabled for 30 sec, and ions with a single charge state as well as an unknown charge state were rejected from fragmentation. An internal lock mass calibration was applied (lock mass 445.12003 Da).

Figure 3: scheme of Q Exactive HF, from Thermo Fisher scientific

After having obtained the results from the MS, in order to decode the spectra, the use of different software/tools was necessary. The first implemented software was Mascot (last version 2.7.0.1), which, using the Proteowizard MSConvert database, transforms the files from the raw format to the **mgf** (mascot generic format) ones and, at the end, into the **dat** format, using the following parameters :

- fixed modifications: Carbamidomethylation, because CAA was used in every protocol and it can modify the peptide mass.
- variable modifications: Oxidation
- trypsin, the type of enzyme that cleaves the proteins
- the peptide charge to take into account, which must be greater than 1⁺ because the source that the Q Exactive HF use is ESI which only produces peptides with 2⁺ charges or more
- 10 ppm mass shifting between theoretical and experimental values
- 0,05 Dalton mass deviation for fragment ions

At this point, the output of Mascot tool, whose files contain the list of peaks, was used to identify peptides using X! Tandem (last version 2017.2.1.4) implemented in Scaffold (last version 5.2.2). Almost exactly the same parameters used for Mascot were set: precursor mass tolerance was set at 10 ppm, and fragment mass tolerance was set at 0,05 Dalton, again, Carbamidomethyl as fixed modifications and Oxidation as variable modifications. It is also fundamental to define the database used:

20240508_FEN_Cluster95_TH_DZ_ATS_20240508, a fen-specific database, which contains 9802858 entries. The identification of proteins and peptides was filtered directly through Scaffold: peptide probability 95%; protein probability 99%; at least 1 identified peptide. To elevate the identification rate (increasing the number of peptide and proteins identified), the false discovery rate can be set to 1% for peptide and 0,1% for proteins. Protein groups were created by combining proteins consisting of similar peptides. The output files are in the **sf3** format.

Then, ProPhane version 6.2.6 was used for proteins taxonomic and functional annotation (Schiebenhoefer et al.,2020); particularly a reference database was used for taxonomic analysis, that is NCBI protein NR, instead, for Functional annotation three databases were used:

- 1) EggNOG, specifically for eukaryotic and prokaryotic proteins
- 2) TIGRFAMs, more specific for bacterial proteins

3) Resfams, specific for antibiotic-resistant proteins

Going into detail, each reference database uses a different search algorithm and a database type that specifies the type of information stored in the respective reference database.

Search Algorithm

- NCBI protein NR uses DIAMOND: a fast alternative to BLAST for protein sequence comparison.
- EggNOG uses EggNOG-mapper (emapper) that assigns protein functions based on orthology.
- TIGRFAMs and Resfams use HMMScan: uses hidden Markov models (HMM) to identify specific protein families.
- Database Type
 - ncbi_nr → non-redundant database for taxonomy
 - eggnog → orthology-based functional database
 - tigrfams → functional protein families
 - resfams_core → antibiotic resistance database

To filter results with high confidence low E-value, LCA method were used in each analysis.

E-value is the expectation value, which represents the probability that a match between the query sequence and the database is random. This parameter is set at 0.001; this lower value means that only highly significant matches are considered.

Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA) method assigns taxonomic classification based on the lowest common ancestor among the results, in this case the LCA threshold is 0.51, which means that at least 51% of the results must agree to assign taxonomy.

Eventually the outputs (txt files) provided by Prophan were implemented in Microsoft Excel, in order to create Pivot tables, which are a very powerful tool, indeed they are used to summarise, analyse and explore large amounts of data, transforming raw data into organised and meaningful information being able to group data by categories,

dates, or other criteria, to get a clear view of trends or relevant information. Moreover, they are extremely flexible and allow us to explore data interactively.

3.13 Upset plots

Upset plots are a data visualisation technique used to analyse and represent sets or collections of sets and their intersections. In bioinformatics or scientific research, upset plots are very useful for comparing several samples that would be difficult to compare using classic Venn diagrams (useful for a few samples). In particular in this study, they were used to study the overlap of proteins between different samples.

Upset plots were generated in JupyterLab (v 4.3.4) using packages upSetR and svglite. Particularly upSetR employs a matrix-based layout to show intersections of sets and their sizes. It is implemented using ggplot2 and allows data analysts to easily generate UpSet plots for their own data. Intersections of sets are visualized as a matrix in which the rows represent the sets and the columns represent their intersections. For each set included in a given intersection, a black-filled circle appears in the corresponding matrix cell. If a set is not part of the intersection, a light grey circle is displayed instead. The intersection sizes are represented by a bar chart positioned above the matrix, aligning each column with a corresponding bar. A second bar chart, displaying the size of each set, is placed to the left of the matrix (Conway et al.,2017).

4 Results

4.1 Comparison of protein extraction protocols

Figure 4: Schematic workflow of the four different protein extraction protocols used and numbers of identified protein groups for each protocol, own graphic

The first aim of the study was to find the best protocol in terms of the quality of the MS spectra and the amount of peptide, and thus, the proteins detected. Therefore, four different published soil protein extraction protocols were chosen, to verify their applicability for agricultural soils. The **figure 4** shows the main steps of the four protocols A, B, B2, C. The Scaffold analysis showed that Protocol B and Protocol B2 were the best in terms of proteins detected, reason being we decided to take only these two into account and study them further. In particular, protocol C was excluded mostly because only a few proteins have been successfully extracted from soil, using different approaches, this was evidenced by visualization of a few bands on SDS-PAGE gels (results not shown).

The second aim of the study was to study and analyse the microbial community of the soils through many tools and software, giving taxonomic and functional information, that through land treatment data, provided directly from the farmers (table 5), it would allow to have a complete overview about the soil quality and health.

4.2 Metaproteome analysis comparison of extraction protocols B and B2 using the standard 100 minutes LC-gradient

Since only protocols B and B2 yielded reasonable protein identifications, these were subjected to a taxonomic and functional annotation of the protein groups using Prophane webtool. In this section, basically, the best extraction protocols are compared, starting from a table which compares the number of proteins found; in particular, it is evident that the output of normal protocol B has given more proteins.

Table 11: Comparison of the number of proteins found in B and in B2 with normal gradient

sample	Protein groups in B	Protein groups in B2.0
FF3R1	5200	3788
GF2R1	5328	4218
BF2R3	5167	3714
EF3R2	4447	3769
AstR2	5004	3933
FstilR2	5027	4432

4.3 Upset plots using the standard 100 minutes LC-gradient

Further and interesting information are provided by the Upset plots. In particular in this study, they were used to study the overlap of proteins between different samples.

Comparing the graphs below (figure 5-6), the second protocol (second UpSet plot) appears to detect more proteins overall, as shown by the higher values in the largest intersections.

The most significant intersection in the first plot contains 1300 proteins, while in the second plot, the largest intersection reaches 1436 proteins. Nevertheless, in both plots, the most frequent intersections involve multiple samples, suggesting that a large portion of the detected proteins is shared.

Moreover, proteins detected in all six samples simultaneously are particularly important, as they likely represent a core set of proteins consistently present across conditions. In both plots, one of the key intersections includes all six samples, but the number of proteins in this category is higher in the second protocol. This suggests that the second protocol might be better at identifying universally present proteins. Also, the second protocol appears to identify more unique proteins, suggesting either greater sensitivity or more variability introduced by the method.

To conclude, using standard LC-gradient, the B2 protocol detects more proteins overall and has a higher number of proteins shared between several samples. It also identifies more unique proteins.

Figure 5: protocol B normal gradient UpSet plot; from JupyterLab

Figure 6: protocol B2 normal gradient UpSet plot, from JupyterLab

4.4 Differences between taxonomic composition using the standard 100 minutes LC-gradient

The final output of the bioinformatic analysis, allowed us to obtain information on the taxonomy of the samples under study, with a special focus on the various phyla present. Going into detail, the use of pivot tables made it possible to organise the enormous amount of data in a simple and precise manner, providing information on the phyla and their relative abundance. The first comparison was made between the two best performing protocols, using a normal gradient to the mass spectrometer.

Figure 7: phyla detected and their relative abundances using protocols B and B2

From figure 7 is evident that the taxonomic composition between B and B2 is fairly identical, except for some phyla found only in protocol B: Candidatus, Shapirobacteria, Chytridiomycota, Evosea, Nucleocytoviricota, Rhodophyta, Rotifera, and one only found in protocol B2 (see table A1, table A2). Nevertheless, all 6 phyla, when present in the samples, contribute merely to 0.1 % of the total or even less. Although all 6 samples came from different soils and underwent two different extraction protocols, it's evident that the main phyla that are: Protobacteria, Actinobacteria, Acidobacteria , Ascomycota and Planctomycetes are preserved in each sample.

4.5 Metaproteome analysis comparison of extraction protocols B and B2 using a 180 minutes LC-gradient

In order to reduce the sample complexity and to increase the identification rates, the same six samples were prepared according to protocols B and B2, but this time they were analysed in the mass spectrometer with a longer gradient in terms of Liquid Chromatography (180 min instead of 100 min). In summary, a longer gradient in liquid chromatography is mainly used to achieve better separation (reducing the overlapping of peaks in the chromatogram) and resolution of compounds (having in fact, more accurate retention times for each compound), especially when dealing with complex samples or compounds with similar properties, as in this case, where the objective is to analyse the soil microbial community.

From the values shown in the table below, it is evident that, as expected, the number of proteins increased considerably in both protocols, even for protocol B2, this number almost doubled. The only discrepant value is that of sample EF3R2 in protocol B, most probably due to errors committed during the preparation of sample's extraction protocol for mass spectrometry.

Table 12: Comparison of the number of proteins found in B and in B2 with longer gradient

sample	Protein groups in B longG	Protein groups in B2 longG
FF3R1	6341	7259
GF2R1	7232	7563
BF2R3	6107	6923
EF3R2	4152	6477
AstR2	6759	7453
FstIR2	6516	7510

4.6 Upset plots using a 180 minutes LC-gradient

Again, in both protocols, the most frequent intersections involve multiple samples, suggesting that a large portion of the detected proteins is shared.

Comparing the two upset plots below (figure 8-9) the maximum number of proteins identified in a sample group is 1865, which is higher than in B (1544), indicating that this protocol captures more proteins overall. Many groups also contain over 1000 shared proteins, but with a slightly more uniform distribution using B2 compared to B. Also, the number of proteins shared across all samples is higher in B2, suggesting greater reproducibility of this protocol. Again, the second protocol appears to identify more unique proteins, suggesting either greater sensitivity or more variability introduced by the method.

To summarize, Protocol B2, using 180 minutes LC-gradient appears to be more effective and reproducible than B. It presents better identification of proteins shared across multiple samples and, the increase in proteins shared across all samples suggests that B2 has higher sensitivity for low-abundance proteins and better uniformity in data collection.

Comparing upset plots obtained with a normal gradient; using a longer gradient: more proteins are detected overall, here is a higher number of proteins found across all groups, the data is more consistent and reproducible. So, considering the upset plots the best protocol of all seems to be the B2 with a longer gradient.

Figure 8: protocol B long gradient UpSet plot, from JupyterLab

4.7 Differences between taxonomic composition using a 180 minutes LC-gradient

After acknowledging that the number of proteins found (see table 10), using a longer gradient had increased considerably, it was important to study whether and how the detected phyla had changed.

Figure 10: Long Gradient, phyla detected and their relative abundances; from excel

Again, compared to the normal gradient MS, the relative abundances between the most prevalent phyla are conserved and in the two different protocols as well. The main phyla represented in figure 10 are Proteobacteria, Acidobacteria, Actinobacteria, Ascomycota, Bacteroidetes and Planctomycetes; however in this case three phyla were found present only in protocol B, respectively: Mollusca, Rhodophyta, Tubilinea; and three

only in B2: Cnidaria, Negarnaviricota, Nucleocytoviricota. Anon, as in the normal gradient, all 6 phyla have a small contribution to the relative abundance in the samples where they were detected, always less than 0,01% (see table A3 and table A4). Some samples show slight shifts in the relative abundance of specific phyla, particularly in Firmicutes, Candidatus Omnitrophica, and Ascomycota.

4.8 Metaproteomic analysis of peat samples

In order to further verify the applicability of the two protocols B and B2 an attempt was made to extract proteins from a more challenging soil type, peatland. Peat is the surface organic layer of a soil that consists of partially decomposed organic matter, derived mostly from plant material, which has accumulated under conditions of waterlogging, oxygen deficiency, high acidity and nutrient deficiency. The peat sample was unique, so two replicates were made for both protocols. Even in samples that were difficult to analyse, protocols B and B2 returned a high number of proteins when looking at the number of proteins identified, with even very close values between the two replicates of each protocol (see table 13).

Considering the Venn diagrams below Protocol B has 3102 shared proteins between Sample 1 and Sample 2, while Protocol B2 has 2469. This shows that Protocol B has more overlap between its two samples, contrary to what seen when studying agricultural soils. Moreover, B2 has a smaller number of total values (6987 vs 7247) and unique values (2033 vs 2049).

Table 13: Comparison of the number of protein groups found in B and in B2 using peat sample

Peat	Protocol B	Protocol B2
Replicate 1	3915	3593
Replicate 2	4332	3394

Figure 11: Venn diagrams showing intersections between the proteins identified in the single Peat sample using protocol B and B2

4.9 Differences between taxonomic composition using peat samples

In addition to try to understand whether the protocols in question were able to extract a good number of proteins from a complicated soil such as peat, a focus was also made on the phyla found and, especially how reproducible these were between and in replicate pairs of the same soil sample.

Figure 12: using a Long Gradient, phyla detected and their relative abundances in peat samples; from excel

The figure 12 clearly shows how similar are to each other the columns that represent phyla for protocol B and the first sample of protocol B2, only the column representing the second sample using the protocol B2 has some differences in relative abundances to all the other protocols, but still retains the main phyla.

In general, the most abundant phyla found in Peat samples are: Proteobacteria, Acidobacteria, Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Planctomycetes, Nitrospirae, Firmicutes.

Going into details, the phyla composition found in both protocols was very similar: a part for Cercozoa, Chytridiomycota, and Haptophyta found only using protocol B, and Duplornaviricota found using protocol B2. Again, all these phyla had a very low relative abundance (see table A5).

4.10 ARGs detection in soil samples

4.9.1 Antibiotic resistance using normal gradient

Antibiotic resistance can have a long-term impact on soil ecosystems, affecting vital processes such as organic decomposition, nitrogen fixation and soil fertility. For this reason, the study of resistance in soils helps to better understand the interaction between human health, animal health and environmental health. Emerging resistances in soil bacteria can propagate through environmental pathways to human pathogenic bacteria.

Figure 13: antibiotic resistance classes identified in the 6 samples using a normal gradient at MS

Contrary to what is shown graphically in the taxonomy of the different samples, in which the abundance of phyla was generally highly conserved, here, analysing the antibiotic resistance classes, the relative abundance can change quite pronouncedly between the various samples (see table A6 and table A7), even slightly, between the same soil sample by comparing the two extraction protocols used (B and B2). However, in

general, the most abundant classes identified are Target Protection, ABC transporter, Beta-lactamase, gene modulating resistance, RND antibiotic efflux, and other efflux.

4.9.2 Antibiotic resistance using long gradient

Obviously, it was also tested whether antibiotic resistance classes were preserved by moving from a normal gradient to a longer gradient.

Figure 14: antibiotic resistance classes identified in the 6 samples using a long gradient at MS

Again, it is evident that the relative abundance of antibiotic resistance classes among different samples is quite different at times, but also among the same samples, see for example AstR2 B and AstR2 B2. (see table A8 and A9)

The main detected classes are: Target protection, ABC transporter, Gene modulating resistance, Beta-lactamase, RND antibiotic efflux, and other efflux. The most abundant antibiotic resistance classes are conserved among the different gradients.

Comparing the presence and abundance of ARGs classes found using the normal and long gradient:

ABC Transporter: ARGs values slightly increased with the longer gradient, except for BF2R3, where they decreased.

Acetyltransferase: The longer gradient shows an increase in values across all samples, suggesting better detection of this resistance.

Beta-Lactamase: Values are generally lower with the longer gradient, except for AstR2 and FstilR2, where they increased.

Gene Modulating Resistance: with the longer gradient, values increase in almost all samples, indicating improved detection.

Glycopeptide Resistance: shows an increase with the longer gradient.

RND Antibiotic Efflux: minimal variations, but a slight decrease in EF3R2.

Target Protection: the value in FF3R1 increased significantly, while in other samples, values remain similar.

Unclassified: values slightly decreased with the longer gradient, indicating a redistribution into specific categories.

Nucleotidyltransferase appears only using longer gradient.

MFS Transporter has a value of zero in some samples in the second table, which might indicate a variation in detection sensitivity.

The longer gradient seems to improve the distinction between resistance mechanisms, reducing the number of unclassified proteins and enhancing the detection of certain classes. However, some categories show lower values compared to the normal gradient, which might be related to method sensitivity.

5 Discussions

5.1 Evaluation of the most performing protocol

Soil is one of the most complicated ecosystems to study. This is why the initial and main aim of the project was to find a valid, robust and efficient protocol for the extraction of proteins from soils. Currently the best approach to study it is through metaproteomic analysis. Particularly, shotgun proteomics, based on high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry, is the most widely used method for large-scale metaproteome characterization (Hettich et al.,2013). However, the low microbial biomass and the presence of abundant interferences in certain soil samples pose significant challenges for mass spectrometry analysis (Gillespie et al.,2011). It has been proven that these techniques require relatively "clean" samples containing detectable levels of proteolytic peptides with minimal interferences, ensuring consistent and high-quality mass spectrometry results (Hettich et al.,2013). The greatest challenge concerns humic substances, which are heterogeneous organic matter produced by microbial metabolisms. They are divided into three main fractions: humin, humic acids, and fulvic acids.

Not only are humic substances known to interfere with protein extraction, purification, and identification/quantification (Arenella et al.,2014). But, Humic acids can also interfere with mass spectrometric measurements by suppressing the electrospray ionization of other analytes. In fact, they contain readily ionizable low-molecular-weight components (below 2000 Da) that are easily detected in ESI mass spectrometry (Piccolo et Spiteller,2003). Also, the cellular lysis is crucial in determining the quality of MS measurements.

Hence the differences in terms of identified proteins (see figure 4) among the protocols is attributable to the different strategies for lysing and extracting proteins among the protocols (see figure 4). ZIP TIP surely helps in removing the humic substances, but, before implementing it in each protocol : beat beading, SDS lysis buffer, FASP, and trypsin were used for protocol A (Chourey et al.,2010; Qian et Hettich.,2017; Wiśniewski, 2017); beat beading, alkaline-SDS extraction buffer, guanidine buffer, FASP, and trypsin were used for protocol B (Chourey et al.,2010; Wiśniewski, 2017; Chourey et Hettich.,2018); and sonication, NaOH extraction solution, and Laemmli treatment buffer were used for protocol C (Herruzo-Ruiz et al.,2021). It was evident that the best performer in terms of proteins identified was protocol B. The worst protocol in

terms of proteins returned by Scaffold was A followed by protocol C. The reasons why the outputs were disappointing could be several.

About protocol A the main reason could be the lack of the use of TCA that guarantees the precipitation of the proteins and the partially removing of humic acids (Nicora et al.,2013). Another possible explanation could be the non-use of PVPP, which contributes to removing humics and soil debris. Also, the lack of the guanidine buffer, that ensures efficient extraction and well-solubilized proteins, probably contributes to the reduction of the detected proteins.

Instead, talking about protocol C, the main problem is probably the absence of Filter-aided sample preparation (FASP) which guarantees the high purity of generated peptides, that is the prerequisite for their successful liquid chromatography fractionation, mass spectrometric sequencing, and protein identification (Wiśniewski .,2017).

Seeing these promising data, protocol B was slightly modified by adding a filtering step through a 10 kDa filter just before the zip-tip procedure. Initially, using a normal gradient the number of proteins detected in the variant was slightly lower than in protocol B, however, by using a longer mobile phase gradient during spectrometer analysis the number of proteins detected in both protocols increased by several thousands - in the variant this number even doubled. This for a purely quantitative argument.

But, the wide range of soil types and the innumerable variations in soil properties could confound the main experimental goal (Chourey et Hettich, 2018); which is why, in addition to the first 6 samples analysed, a peat sample was tested, which in fact confirmed the validity of the protocol B/B2 for each soil type (table 13).

5.2 Taxonomic evaluation of data

With the main goal achieved and acknowledged, the study focused on the phyla found, trying to understand how the use of the different protocols can affect this type of results. Redundancies in protein sequences and functionality are common in complex natural communities; however, recent advances in metaproteomics can connect the expression of certain proteins, or protein pathways, to the appropriate microbial members in the community (Hettich et al., 2013). This especially thanks to software and well assembled metagenome databases developed in recent years.

Protocols B and B2 (normal and long gradient), were considered. The main phyla, returned by Scaffold, were always preserved (see figure 7, figure10, figure 12) not only between the protocols and their different gradients, but also between the different samples themselves. This further confirms the validity and the value of the protocols developed. In order to see more pronounced differences between the soil samples in question, sampling over much longer time intervals may be necessary.

The structure of the microbial community of the studied soils at the level of phylum is shown in Fig. 7 and 10. The main dominant phyla found were Proteobacteria (around 40%) and Actinobacteria (20-15 %). An average predominance was noted for the phyla Planctomycetes (3-5%), Acidobacteria (4-5 %), Ascomycota (2-5 %), Gemmatimonadetes (3.5 %), Verrucomicrobia (1-2 %), Firmicutes (1-4%), Bacteroidetes (1.5-2.5%). According to Wang et al. (2018), the dominant bacterial taxa in the rhizosphere of many plants include Actinobacteria, Acidobacteria, Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes. All of the above taxa were found in the microbiome of the studied soils, and were the dominant bacterial phyla.

The Proteobacteria phylum dominated in all the samples under study. Proteobacteria are evolutionarily, geologically, and ecologically important phylum of microorganisms. Members of this phylum are extremely diverse in terms of metabolism. These include chemoautotrophic, chemoorganotrophic, and phototrophic microorganisms, which represent the majority of the known bacteria of medical, industrial, and agricultural importance (Marín et al., 2015).

Actinobacteria is the second largest phylum found. In soil ecosystems, actinobacteria perform multiple essential functions. Among these, they produce a broad spectrum of compounds and metabolites that support plant growth, even under challenging

environmental conditions like nutrient deficiencies, drought, salinity, and soils contaminated with potentially toxic elements (PTE). Their biodegradation activities are crucial for the recycling of organic matter (Yadav, 2021). Actinobacteria play a key role in agriculture by producing organic acids, fixing atmospheric nitrogen, and breaking down organic matter (Bhatti et al., 2017). They significantly influence agricultural productivity and mineral cycling by decomposing plant biomass and chelating minerals in the soil (Salwan and Sharma, 2020).

Acidobacteria that was found in a relevant percentage (between 4% and 5%), have been suggested to play a role in soil restoration as they are beneficial for soil nutrient cycling and plant growth following severe disturbances (Huang et al., 2015). It has been shown that acidobacteria are tolerant to various pollutants, such as PCBs and petroleum compounds, linear alkylbenzene sulfonate, p-nitrophenol (Sanchez-Peinado et al., 2010), and heavy metals (Barns et al., 2007). This suggest that acidobacteria may be involved in the degradation of certain pollutants and explain why acidobacteria prevailed in the soils contaminated with PAHs (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons) and heavy metals.

The abundance of bacteria of the phylum Acidobacteria is approximately the same as that of Planctomycetes. These classes include aerobic and anaerobic chemoorganotrophic planctomycetes, which use a wide variety of organic compounds as carbon and energy sources.

The phylum Firmicutes is represented in the studied soils in a fairly wide range of 1%–4%. Firmicutes are one of the most common phyla of bacteria that inhabit the plant rhizosphere. Members of the phylum Firmicutes are extremely useful microorganisms in agroecology. Various genera and species belonging to this phylum have been isolated from different environments. Firmicutes have shown many beneficial plant activities even in extreme environmental conditions (temperature, salinity, metal pollution). Representatives of this phylum can either directly or indirectly promote the germination, rooting, and growth of plants, even under the influence of various stress biotic (pathogen pressure) and abiotic factors (temperature, salt, or metal content) (Hashmi et al., 2020). Note the fact that this phylum was always present at higher concentrations in GF2R1.

The bacteria of the Bacteroidetes phylum were found in the studied soils in amounts from 1.5 % to 2,5 %. Bacteroidetes are usually one of the dominant phyla in soil microbiota. They are the important and dominant carbohydrate breakers. Bacteroidetes thrive on their ability to secrete different sets of carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) that target a wide variety of glycans in the soil (Larsbrink et al.,2014).

The phylum, Verrucomicrobia (1-2%), makes an important contribution to the carbon cycle in the Earth's ecosystems.

To sum up, as the number of proteins detected between the two protocols, and as the kind of phyla identified, and their relative abundance were pretty the same among the protocols results and analysis, we can affirm that the protocols are reliable and interchangeable. This lack of statistically significant differences between the two protocols, B and B2, suggests that the type of analysis might need more detail.

After determining the microbial content of the soil, the next step was to integrate these data with information on soil treatment (table 5), looking for possible correlations in the literature. It is common knowledge that some agronomic practices affect soil microbial communities and functions. Microorganisms have been shown to improve plant development by secreting metabolites, mobilizing nutrients, and alleviating biotic and abiotic stresses and the most diverse crop rotation showed the most diverse and active soil microbial biota (Thair et al.,2017; D'Acunto et al.,2018).

Crop rotation can profoundly influence the soil microbial community, much more than the fertilization regime. In fact, the right crop rotation can modify the soil community, with favourable impacts on agronomic performance (Xie et al.,2022; Bolaji et al.,2021), which means higher profit for the farmer. Cultural rotation has been shown to allow a higher total organic carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium content compared to monocultures (Sun et al.,2023). Similarly to this study, Bolaji et al.,2021 reported that the main phyla of the soil microbial community in crop rotation systems were Proteobacteria, Acidobacteria, and Actinobacteria; instead considering only the fungal community Ascomycota and Basidiomycota were the most abundant.

In this study, despite the few differences in composition between the different samples analysed, some observations can be made: the samples with the greatest taxonomic diversity appear to be those with the greatest crop variability over the years (e.g. BF2R3: winter wheat → winter rape →sugar beet); soils treated with cow manure

(EF3R2) show a higher abundance of Nitrospirae and Planctomycetes, both groups involved in the nitrogen cycle. This could be due to the increased supply of organic matter and nutrients provided by the manure. In contrast, soils treated with conventional mineral fertilisers (FF3R1, GF2R1, BF2R3) show a dominance of Proteobacteria and Actinobacteria, vgroups typically associated with soils richer in chemical inputs. Moreover, the AStR2 and FStilR2 samples, although not cultivated during the period covered by the study, show a microbial community very similar to those found in the others, thus suggesting significant agricultural use of these soils shortly before the start of data collection.

5.3 Analysis of the microbial community composition in peat soils

Peatlands are one of the largest atmospheric carbon sinks and CH₄ sources.

Specifically northern peatlands have played an important role in global C cycles and climate change throughout the Holocene (Kurnianto et al.,2015).

In this study, the only peatland sample considered was analysed by LC-MS to see if the B and B2 protocols also gave positive results with different soil types. Again, thousands of proteins were identified (table 13), divided into around 30 phyla (figure 12), indicating that a rich microbial community was captured.

The most abundant phyla, such as Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, Acidobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Firmicutes, have frequently been detected as dominant groups in other peatland ecosystems (Pankratov et al.,2005; Andersen et al.,2013).

Methane production is a consequence of the permanently waterlogged condition of the peat layers, in fact abundance of methanogenic bacteria is significantly higher than in normal soil samples; only Proteobacteria represents almost 50% of the relative abundance.

Since bacterial diversity and composition in peatlands vary as a function of peat depth and its associated physical-chemical properties (Zhou et al., 2017), it would be interesting to analyse other peat bogs with the tested protocols, perhaps at different depths.

5.4 Antibiotic Resistances mechanisms detected in agricultural soils

Antibiotic resistance, considered one of the most important threats to public health, has been receiving increasing attention in recent years. The use of antibiotic in animal production can result in a selection of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in these animals. The transfer of antibiotic-resistant bacteria from animals to humans can occur either directly, through contact with animals and the consumption of animal products, or indirectly via the environment (Kuppusamy et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2005; Heuer et al., 2011). Previous studies describe an increased number of resistance genes in soils due to fertilization with animal manure (Heuer et al., 2011a; Cycoń et al., 2019) or the use of inorganic fertilizers (Wang et al., 2023).

As expected, the relative abundance of unclassified proteins, meaning that the proteins were not assigned as resistance proteins, was higher in samples AstR2 and FstIR2 (see figure 13-14). These samples, belonging to the only two uncultivated and unfertilised samples, indicate a significantly lower selective pressure for antibiotic resistance than soils treated with mineral fertilisers or manure.

The samples analysed had more or less the same ARGs but with different abundances (see also tables A6,A7,A8,A9), in fact the samples treated with mineral and conventional fertilizers showed the highest abundance of Target Protection and ABC transporter ARGs. The most abundant ARG classes were: Target Protection (1,9-10,9%); ABC transporter (1-2,5%); Beta-lactamase (0,09-0,83%); Gene modulating resistance (0,16-0,72%); RND antibiotic efflux (0,09-0,66%).

The use of animal feces as organic fertilizer is a common practice. This is followed by the composting process that leads to an increase in the abundance of *Bacillus* spp. It has been established that *Bacillus* spp. serve as host bacteria for resistance genes associated with tetracyclines, sulfonamides, and β -lactams (Qi et al., 2023). Indeed, a greater abundance of β -lactamase, efflux and gene-modulating resistance ARGs was detected in the only soil treated with cow manure (EFR2) compared to those treated with conventional fertilization.

The study on ARGs further confirm that the type of treatment (cultivated or non-cultivated), the type of crop (such as sugar cane, corn, wheat, rye, rape), as well as the type of fertilization (conventional, using chalk or mineral, with cow manure) profoundly influences their presence within microbial communities in soils, increasing or decreasing their abundance much more than their variety; once again proving to be a serious threat

to public health and one of the greatest challenges facing humanity in the years to come.

6 Outlook

The B and B2 protocols are certainly high-performance, reliable and reproducible, whether at a long gradient or not, but the amount of data and information that could be obtained was so extensive that a master's thesis project is by no means sufficient to analyse everything in depth. Not only protein extraction protocols need to be optimized and adjusted for the soil samples, but also mass spectrometry parameters can also influence the results and thus different MS parameters can be tested (LC-gradient, length of LC-column; collecting times for ions in MS etc).

Moreover, given the extreme relevance of the topic and the number of ARGs classified by these protocols, soils should be studied for longer periods (at least five years) in order to better understand how ARGs are affected over time under different conditions and treatments. At the same time, possible changes in the microbiological communities must be monitored.

For these reasons, it would be desirable for these protocols to be used for longer-term projects.

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8 List of figures

Figure 1: Soil organisms grouped by class, showing the size of body width.....	8
Figure 2: metaproteomic analysis scheme.....	23
Figure 3: scheme of Q Exactive HF.....	36
Figure 4: Schematic workflow of the four different protein extraction protocols used and numbers of identified protein groups for each protocol.....	40
Figure 5: protocol B normal gradient UpSet plot	44
Figure 6: protocol B2 normal gradient UpSet plot	45
Figure 7: phyla detected and their relative abundances using protocols B and B2.....	46
Figure 8: protocol B long gradient UpSet plot.....	50
Figure 9: protocol B2 long gradient UpSet plot.....	51
Figure 10: Long Gradient, phyla detected and their relative abundances.....	52
Figure 11: Venn diagrams showing intersections between the proteins identified in the single Peat sample using protocol B (left) and B2 (right).....	54
Figure 12: using a Long Gradient, phyla detected and their relative abundances in peat sample.....	55
Figure 13: antibiotic resistance classes identified in the 6 samples using a normal gradient at MS.....	57
Figure 14: antibiotic resistance classes identified in the 6 samples using a long gradient at MS.....	58

9 List of tables

Table 1: list of substances used during the study.....	17
Table 2: list of consumables used during the study.....	18
Table 3: list of instruments used during the study.....	19
Table 4: informatic tools used during the study.....	21
Table 5: information on the treatment of the soils under study over the past three years.....	22
Table 6: solution used for the protein extraction according to Protocol A.....	25
Table 7: table that shows the supernatant left for each sample and the correspondent amount of TCA added afterwards.....	27
Table 8: solution used for the protein extraction according to Protocol B (and B2).....	29
Table 9: solution used for the protein extraction according to Protocol C.....	32
Table 10: Solution used for Zip-Tip desaltin.....	34
Table 11: Comparison of the number of proteins found in B and in B2 with normal gradient.....	42
Table 12: Comparison of the number of proteins found in B and in B2 with longer gradient.....	48
Table 13: Comparison of the number of proteins found in B and in B2 using peat sample.....	54

10 Acknowledgements

First of all, I would like to thank Daniela Zühlke, who gave me the opportunity to have the most formative experience of my life so far, the one who was always helpful, kind, patient and present throughout my research time in Greifswald. I would also like to thank my lab mates, the people in the microbiology department at the University of Greifswald, but also the whole community in the wonderful city where I was a guest, who made me feel at home even though I was actually thousands of kilometres away. Obviously, I would like to thank Professor Pessione, whose contacts and knowledge created this opportunity.

I should not overlook all the moral and other support I received during my studies from my girlfriend Chiara, my family and my friends in Oria.

Last but not least, I would like to thank Giuliano, Lorenzo, Riccardo, Nicola, Pierpaolo, Daniele and Federico, the best course mates I could ever wish for, who made the exams easier to pass, the lessons less boring and made my free time and my stay in Turin more enjoyable.

11 Supplementary material

Table A1: phyla abundance in protocol B using normal gradient

Phylum	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstilR2
Acidobacteria	0.04906	0.041944	0.03257	0.052736	0.048085	0.045802
Actinobacteria	0.225577	0.198933	0.230982	0.148994	0.150239	0.131616
Arthropoda	0.001106	0.000904	0.005968	0.001351	0.000971	0.024521
Ascomycota	0.033794	0.032989	0.039178	0.043899	0.041006	0.053041
Bacillariophyta	0.001015	0.000694	0.001561	0.001171	0.000415	0.000737
Bacteroidetes	0.014711	0.01205	0.021838	0.014256	0.017064	0.018362
Basidiomycota	0.004263	0.003673	0.00603	0.006964	0.006645	0.008916
Blastocladiomycota	0.000521	0.000476	0.001449	0.000135	0.000909	0.001581
Candidatus Omnitrophica	0.000227	0.00022	0	0	0	0.000427
Candidatus						
Shapirobacteria	0.000119	0	0	0	0	0
Cercozoa	0.000308	0.000503	0	0.000381	0	0.000597
Chlamydiae	0.001402	0.000828	0.001072	0.001509	0.002432	0.001178
Chloroflexi	0.004919	0.005102	0.004363	0.005307	0.006029	0.004135
Chlorophyta	0.010456	0.010372	0.016635	0.017197	0.014202	0.018472
Chordata	0.012524	0.009625	0.014321	0.022188	0.014177	0.014953
Chytridiomycota	0	0	9.63E-05	0	0	0
Ciliophora	0.002048	0.003711	0.002289	0.003948	0.002862	0.004176
Cyanobacteria	0.001285	0.000517	0.000357	0.000637	0.000241	0.000719
Endomyxa	0.000663	0.000662	0.000386	0.00074	0.00049	0.000737
Euglenozoa	0.000396	0.000249	0.000369	0.000583	0.000227	0.000492
Euryarchaeota	0.000661	0.001718	0.001745	0.001364	0.003148	0.004296
Evosea	0	0	0	0.000419	0	0
Fibrobacteres	0.000454	0.001322	0.000405	0.001154	0.001354	0.00077
Firmicutes	0.015967	0.043016	0.021918	0.018143	0.019292	0.015003
Fusobacteria	0.002295	0.002256	0.002798	0.002603	0.002113	0.002526
Gemmatimonadetes	0.004239	0.006971	0.005892	0.008117	0.006757	0.007256
Haptophyta	0	0	0	0.000618	0.000502	0.000509
Heterolobosea	0.001224	0.000929	0.001505	0.001773	0.001844	0.001244
Ignavibacteriae	0.000716	0.000563	0.000423	0.000252	0	0.000824
Kiritimatiellaeota	0.002108	0.000867	0.000523	0.002616	0.000973	0.0004

Mucoromycota	0.003541	0.002443	0.006235	0.004794	0.005396	0.006419
Nitrospirae	0.016048	0.014606	0.01203	0.010997	0.013288	0.008684
Nucleocytoviricota	0	0	0.001077	0	0	0
Oomycota	0.005575	0.004011	0.00866	0.004676	0.005771	0.004959
Planctomycetes	0.033106	0.030124	0.025559	0.029768	0.033957	0.046455
Proteobacteria	0.38619	0.40256	0.363473	0.42761	0.425065	0.40987
Rhodophyta	0	0	0	0.00039	0	0
Rotifera	0	0	0.000126	0	0	0
Spirochaetes	0.003198	0.003521	0.003072	0.004733	0.002611	0.001677
Streptophyta	0.014634	0.012329	0.018282	0.012459	0.028507	0.025062
Tenericutes	0.001088	0.002256	0.001261	0.001234	0.001061	0.000908
Thaumarchaeota	0.016514	0.011426	0.008958	0.003374	0.007689	0.001434
unclassified	0.089889	0.097326	0.088	0.090682	0.085458	0.077235
Uroviricota	5.19E-05	0	5.54E-05	0	0	0.000234
various	0.02246	0.023519	0.038968	0.038774	0.035609	0.045277
Verrucomicrobia	0.015646	0.014787	0.009572	0.011452	0.013611	0.008496

Table A2: phyla abundance in protocol B2 using normal gradient

Phylum	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstilR2
Acidobacteria	0.04843	0.04375	0.03248642	0.05187	0.03698799	0.0403822
Actinobacteria	0.19600	0.19516	0.19732806	0.15303	0.15429497	0.1327931
Arthropoda	0.00155	0.00706	0.00727576	0.0024	0.00259599	0.0388847
Ascomycota	0.02787	0.02262	0.03270700	0.03004	0.02921302	0.0323801
Bacillariophyta	0.00149	0.00083	0.00095076	0.00233	0.00058330	0.0015620
Bacteroidetes	0.01674	0.01518	0.01535397	0.01320	0.01661626	0.0172778
Basidiomycota	0.00448	0.00492	0.00266396	0.00529	0.00453939	0.0150073
Blastocladiomycota	0.00038	0.00119	0.00033208	0.00027	0.00040801	0.0014481
Candidatus						
Omnitrophica	0.00041	0.00026	0	0	0.00014596	0.0006691
Cercozoa	0	0.00037	0.00092934	0.00090	0.00044891	0.0015512
Chlamydiae	0.00030	0.00093	0.00079384	0.00105	0.00067173	0.0009373
Chloroflexi	0.00520	0.00512	0.00364675	0.00434	0.00283614	0.0020254
Chlorophyta	0.01073	0.0152	0.0099576	0.00992	0.01417784	0.0158190
Chordata	0.0168	0.00853	0.01967740	0.0156	0.01790054	0.0163988
Ciliophora	0.0040	0.00283	0.00342387	0.00431	0.00423928	0.0068854
Cyanobacteria	0.00046	0.0012	0.00046786	0.00063	0.00083821	0.0002525
Endomyxa	0.00026	0.00056	0.00074407	0.00042	0.00040881	0.0002274
Euglenozoa	0	0	0	0.00021	0	0.0001489
Euryarchaeota	0.00122	0.00292	0.00167230	0.00260	0.00232284	0.0025415
Fibrobacteres	0.0007	6.3E-05	0.00059935	0.00090	0.00039758	0.0004575
Firmicutes	0.01579	0.03557	0.01982977	0.02036	0.01335312	0.0101188
Fusobacteria	0.00257	0.00332	0.00085550	0.00080	0.001375	0.0009243
Gemmatimonadetes	0.00747	0.00518	0.00547519	0.00437	0.00514295	0.0063515
Haptophyta	0.00034	0	0	0	5.5383E-05	0
Heterolobosea	0.00177	0.00265	0.00258123	0.00229	0.00188091	0.00148604
Ignavibacteriae	0.00092	0.00049	0	0.00014	0	0.00070961
Kiritimatiellaeota	0.00052	0.00050	0.00036358	0.00068	0.00021908	0.00033710
Mollusca	0	0	9.1328E-05	0	0	0
Mucoromycota	0.00237	0.00312	0.00320096	0.00189	0.00397742	0.00455012
Nitrospirae	0.02483	0.02297	0.01369690	0.01865	0.01020334	0.00904162
Oomycota	0.00382	0.00908	0.00581739	0.00666	0.00888153	0.00866226
Planctomycetes	0.0377	0.02964	0.02533643	0.03373	0.03736869	0.04452826
Proteobacteria	0.38397	0.37125	0.43135583	0.4468	0.44151345	0.41494054
Spirochaetes	0.00456	0.00400	0.00120573	0.00214	0.00215135	0.00318420

Streptophyta	0.01916	0.02431	0.01640570	0.01918	0.03655783	0.02298007
Tenericutes	0.0009	0.00186	0.00353263	0	0.00066459	0.0008106
Thaumarchaeota	0.01228	0.01152	0.00850675	0.00492	0.0061223	0.0019201
unclassified	0.10064	0.10601	0.08620468	0.09416	0.091239	0.08838583
Uroviricota	0	0	0	0	0	5.0803E-05
various	0.0272	0.02345	0.03467275	0.02811	0.03619683	0.04406049
Verrucomicrobia	0.01557	0.01618	0.00985706	0.01554	0.0134694	0.00930728

Table A3: phyla abundance in protocol B using long gradient

Phylum	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstilR2
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Acidobacteria	0.044437	0.03699	0.035327	0.055105	0.054412	0.044163
Actinobacteria	0.191864	0.178162	0.206993	0.130366	0.170738	0.140288
Arthropoda	0.001462	0.002714	0.003626	0.002093	0.001488	0.016832
Ascomycota	0.025684	0.024276	0.03046	0.036746	0.033355	0.030921
Bacillariophyta	0.001391	0.000914	0.002349	0.001315	0.000454	0.000897
Bacteroidetes	0.019429	0.021135	0.030699	0.02938	0.022454	0.02358
Basidiomycota	0.003103	0.004073	0.004729	0.002441	0.006429	0.009365
Blastocladiomycota	0	0.000578	0.000679	0.000333	0.000546	0.001018
Candidatus						
Omnitrophica	0.00021	0.000227	9.78E-05	0	0	0.000355
Cercozoa	0.000284	0.00036	0	0	0	0.000991
Chlamydiae	0.000394	0.000263	0.00064	0.000645	0.000871	0.0006
Chloroflexi	0.005501	0.004645	0.005533	0.001877	0.004586	0.004997
Chlorophyta	0.016171	0.019879	0.024681	0.012043	0.011345	0.018874
Chordata	0.013015	0.00844	0.024046	0.039725	0.011754	0.016618
Chytridiomycota	8.32E-05	0.000125	0.000176	0	0	7.63E-05
Ciliophora	0.001837	0.002395	0.001741	0.002001	0.001434	0.003679
Cyanobacteria	0.000655	0.000536	0.000308	0.000965	0.000421	0.000225
Endomyxa	0.000601	0.000283	0.000147	0.002405	0.000222	0.000158
Euglenozoa	0	0.000754	0.000313	0	0.000488	0.000318
Euryarchaeota	0.001941	0.000866	0.001044	0.004253	0.00207	0.002629
Fibrobacteres	0.001935	0.002137	0.001612	0.001462	0.000964	0.00073
Firmicutes	0.019233	0.04689	0.023951	0.025942	0.01962	0.017246
Fusobacteria	0.001536	0.001465	0.001271	0.001212	0.001341	0.001566
Gemmatimonadetes	0.007275	0.004614	0.004168	0.003691	0.006358	0.002872
Haptophyta	0.000317	0.000281	0.000396	0.000731	0.00032	0.000344
Heterolobosea	0.002181	0.001021	0.001299	0.000376	0.001404	0.001278
Ignavibacteriae	0.000177	0.000433	0.0005	0	0.000125	0.000206
Kiritimatiellaeota	0.001936	0.001079	0.000477	0.001598	0.001062	0.000286
Mollusca	0	0	0	7.69E-05	0	0
Mucoromycota	0.002367	0.003293	0.00367	0.003007	0.004018	0.004507
Nitrospirae	0.020785	0.018842	0.013444	0.018338	0.011521	0.010097
Oomycota	0.005705	0.008918	0.007075	0.012597	0.005861	0.00942
Planctomycetes	0.027823	0.031239	0.031224	0.02966	0.037656	0.040126
Proteobacteria	0.409512	0.391538	0.36237	0.411328	0.43364	0.444347
Rhodophyta	0	0	0.000308	0	0	0.000267

Spirochaetes	0.003174	0.003133	0.004617	0.002624	0.002418	0.002259
Streptophyta	0.018171	0.022375	0.013356	0.012502	0.025953	0.019097
Tenericutes	0.001137	0.001397	0.000436	0.000215	0.000805	0.000132
Thaumarchaeota	0.011344	0.012152	0.008005	0.004793	0.00927	0.001602
Tubulinea	0	0	0	0	0.00012	0
unclassified	0.103972	0.103077	0.096686	0.080859	0.081007	0.080568
Uroviricota	5.49E-05	0	0	0	0	4.1E-05
various	0.01839	0.022699	0.040988	0.057257	0.024861	0.038827
Verrucomicrobia	0.01491	0.015802	0.010556	0.010036	0.008608	0.007597

Table A4: phyla abundance in Protocol B2 using long gradient

Phylum	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstilR2
Acidobacteria	0.040825	0.02641	0.030213	0.046053	0.049312	0.038743

Actinobacteria	0.1789	0.163073	0.199335	0.147708	0.154754	0.135987
Arthropoda	0.000983	0.006983	0.00529	0.001767	0.002844	0.029536
Ascomycota	0.032125	0.03757	0.040501	0.053607	0.04488	0.044731
Bacillariophyta	0.000397	0.001362	0.00077	0.001928	0.000838	0.000778
Bacteroidetes	0.015506	0.01418	0.022083	0.020182	0.019046	0.017593
Basidiomycota	0.004761	0.005481	0.004942	0.008111	0.007636	0.014227
Blastocladiomycota	0.000573	0.000702	0.001074	0.001075	0.000917	0.002013
Candidatus						
Omnitrophica	9.85E-05	9.92E-05	0.000117	0.00023	9.94E-05	0.000727
Cercozoa	0	0.000263	0.000899	0.00064	0.000515	0.001017
Chlamydiae	0.000495	0.000787	0.000641	0.000871	0.001164	0.000466
Chloroflexi	0.005784	0.005841	0.00536	0.00715	0.007552	0.007788
Chlorophyta	0.012408	0.018286	0.012297	0.01769	0.015022	0.0151
Chordata	0.010849	0.008621	0.015352	0.01517	0.010274	0.009912
Chytridiomycota	0	0.000277	0	9.59E-05	0	0.000223
Ciliophora	0.001107	0.002293	0.002738	0.001987	0.002367	0.0037
Cnidaria	0	0	0	0	0	0.000177
Cyanobacteria	0.000133	0.000952	0.000502	0.001009	0.001035	0
Endomyxa	0.000556	0.00104	0.000142	0.000447	0.000701	0.000686
Euglenozoa	0.000218	0.00022	0	0.000887	0.000473	0.000337
Euryarchaeota	0.000938	0.00061	0.001322	0.002857	0.001177	0.001087
Fibrobacteres	0.000339	0.000352	0.000589	0.000803	0.000542	0.00018
Firmicutes	0.014218	0.027642	0.018975	0.017893	0.016158	0.010193
Fusobacteria	0.001484	0.003222	0.001929	0.002035	0.002789	0.00306
Gemmatimonadetes	0.007836	0.006362	0.006174	0.006064	0.007207	0.007832
Haptophyta	0	0.000235	0	0	0	0
Heterolobosea	0.00075	0.002856	0.001753	0.001797	0.00228	0.001222
Ignavibacteriae	0.000257	0.000182	9.92E-05	0.000184	0.000492	0.000478
Kiritimatiellaeota	0.00128	0.000639	0.00066	0.000757	0.000511	0.000641
Mucoromycota	0.003164	0.004228	0.002603	0.007307	0.006145	0.005993
Negarnaviricota	0	4.03E-05	0	0	0	0
Nitrospirae	0.021251	0.018813	0.012518	0.013723	0.015879	0.010559
Nucleocytoviricota	0.000161	0	0.001218	0	0	0.00013
Oomycota	0.00815	0.006438	0.006133	0.008108	0.009263	0.006269
Planctomycetes	0.037748	0.033659	0.024277	0.035054	0.043707	0.045787
Proteobacteria	0.424997	0.409105	0.411703	0.417682	0.410618	0.440387

Spirochaetes	0.003212	0.002143	0.003114	0.002969	0.002251	0.002752
Streptophyta	0.021138	0.037803	0.022604	0.023609	0.031617	0.024164
Tenericutes	0.000666	0.001868	0.001067	0.001996	0.000649	0.000285
Thaumarchaeota	0.008961	0.008063	0.009775	0.004078	0.00573	0.001568
unclassified	0.102259	0.10123	0.09218	0.092861	0.086934	0.08004
Uroviricota	8.82E-05	0	0	0	4.45E-05	3.57E-05
various	0.023545	0.024359	0.030157	0.023014	0.023929	0.027678
Verrucomicrobia	0.01184	0.015712	0.008895	0.010605	0.012648	0.005916

Table A5: phyla abundance among the replicates of the peat sample

phylum	B sample 1	B sample 2	B2 sample1	B2 sample2
Acidobacteria	0.043749	0.04982	0.040103	0.038335
Actinobacteria	0.066392	0.06477	0.062143	0.060101

Arthropoda	0.000712	0.000854	0.000793	0.00116
Ascomycota	0.02322	0.023488	0.025348	0.026019
Bacillariophyta	0.000976	0.000568	0.001809	0.001769
Bacteroidetes	0.04981	0.022448	0.031859	0.017551
Basidiomycota	0.002469	0.002225	0.009359	0.007722
Blastocladiomycota	0.000136	0.000229	0.000605	0.000964
Candidatus Omnitrophica	0	0.000169	0.000271	0
Chlamydiae	0.001831	0.000877	0.001251	0.000514
Chloroflexi	0.004028	0.004592	0.003955	0.004113
Chlorophyta	0.012344	0.01134	0.020257	0.021702
Chordata	0.020804	0.016135	0.015625	0.044457
Ciliophora	0.001368	0.001846	0.005977	0.005201
Cyanobacteria	0	0.001167	8.35E-05	0.000137
Endomyxa	0.000243	0	0.000576	0.000192
Euglenozoa	0	0.000116	0.000602	0.000649
Euryarchaeota	0.005897	0.008057	0.006346	0.007856
Fibrobacteres	0.002151	0.002179	0.000629	0.000968
Firmicutes	0.039952	0.034751	0.018027	0.018884
Fusobacteria	0.004	0.002553	0.001103	0.001704
Gemmatimonadetes	0.008604	0.007445	0.006425	0.005335
Heterolobosea	0.000192	0.000517	0.000954	0.001881
Ignavibacteriae	0.001586	0.001308	0.000998	0.000767
Kiritimatiellaeota	0.00137	0.001713	0.000792	0.001808
Mucoromycota	0.001647	0.001692	0.003386	0.003982
Nitrospirae	0.021565	0.023744	0.031995	0.02348
Nucleocytoviricota	0	0.000132	0	0.000152
Oomycota	0.002581	0.004747	0.00625	0.007809
Planctomycetes	0.024175	0.019201	0.032139	0.028507
Proteobacteria	0.463546	0.48916	0.448958	0.413212
Spirochaetes	0.003696	0.003159	0.005422	0.003387
Streptophyta	0.007952	0.011896	0.029982	0.031227
Tenericutes	0.001826	0.002267	0.002264	0.001463
Thaumarchaeota	0.006231	0.006762	0.009409	0.009435
unclassified	0.118164	0.129965	0.127137	0.106438
Uroviricota	6.85E-05	0	6.67E-05	0
various	0.03574	0.026278	0.022702	0.086741

Verrucomicrobia	0.020351	0.021011	0.024395	0.014289
Cercozoa	0.00049	0.000448	0	0
Chytridiomycota	0	0.000244	0	0
Haptophyta	0.000136	0.000124	0	0
Duplornaviricota	0	0	0	8.96E-05

Table A6: Abundance of antibiotic classes in protocol B using normal gradient

ANTIBIOTIC						
CLASS	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstilR2
ABC Transporter	0.021273553	0.020120356	0.020382784	0.017616894	0.014653146	0.015510458
Acetyltransferase	0	0.00019988	0.001499031	0.000692347	0.000986183	0.001008307

Antibiotic						
Inactivation	0.000633212	0.000799248	0.000250587	0.000483317	0.0010157	0.000356744
Beta-Lactamase	0.001567872	0.003507408	0.00508749	0.007578049	0.004072549	0.007768651
Gene Modulating						
Resistance	0.004773571	0.003732899	0.002802565	0.002712179	0.00167821	0.002272923
Glycopeptide						
Resistance	0.000970554	0.001799	0.000339153	0.000998591	0.000533277	0.000397548
MFS Transporter	6.21039E-05	0.000120476	0.000859677	0.000663384	0.000687067	0.000651913
Other Efflux	0.002507632	0.003011868	0.002201494	0.001798447	0.00291117	0.004504851
Phosphotransferase	0.000818198	0.001135673	0.001780805	0.00130657	0.001527654	0.002163706
Quinolone						
Resistance	0.000377254	0	0.000301683	0.000303716	0.00129003	0.000101745
RND Antibiotic						
Efflux	0.001225233	0.001899904	0.002363593	0.00334265	0.003486194	0.003809126
rRNA						
Methyltransferase	0.000852215	0.001124794	0.00052736	0.000744419	0.000665615	0.000898437
Target Protection	0.050228974	0.055540998	0.048825292	0.048096629	0.037670494	0.030970948
unclassified	0.914709628	0.907007494	0.912778486	0.913563708	0.92882271	0.929584644
various	0	0	0	9.91007E-05	0	0

Table A7: Abundance of antibiotic classes in protocol B2 using normal gradient

ANTIBIOTIC						
CLASS	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstIIIR2
ABC Transporter	0.02156438	0.021558251	0.017591848	0.021054359	0.023315953	0.018897345
Acetyltransferase	0.000461335	0.000920137	0.000842051	0.001673275	0.001471313	0.000566751
Antibiotic Inactivation	0.001301549	0.0007117	0.000359851	0.00023684	0.000481657	0.00069696
Beta-Lactamase	0.000907985	0.002198597	0.002298251	0.002418029	0.003113357	0.005275153
Gene Modulating						
Resistance	0.004955441	0.006281981	0.003335058	0.00688668	0.005881388	0.002930007
Glycopeptide						
Resistance	0.004262653	0.004503921	0.002214347	0.001430137	0.003284482	0.002522875
MFS Transporter	0	0.000363133	0.000503935	0.000857681	0	0.000481377
Nucleotidyltransferase	0	0	0	0.000643983	0	0.000834534
Other Efflux	0.002686853	0.004176278	0.005004556	0.005682943	0.007027015	0.002362526
Phosphotransferase	0.000784948	0.001702699	0.002574919	0.001082296	0.000297737	0.00339581
Quinolone Resistance	0	0	0	0.000166428	0	0.000114359
RND Antibiotic Efflux	0.000978711	0.001772709	0.004035991	0.002591043	0.0030909	0.003128754
rRNA						
Methyltransferase	0.000619413	0	0.000646282	0	0.000562371	0.000361414
Target Protection	0.108806075	0.059216537	0.038833065	0.048146839	0.039021591	0.036829979
unclassified	0.852506509	0.896594057	0.921759847	0.907129468	0.912452236	0.921602154
various	0.000164149	0	0	0	0	0

Table A8: Abundance of antibiotic classes in protocol B using long gradient

ANTIBIOTIC						
CLASS	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstilR2
ABC Transporter	0.02555821	0.02122873	0.02022423	0.01007296	0.02007616	0.01676834
Acetyltransferase	0.00144947	0.00071438	0.00081104	0.00017255	0.00028794	0.00098574
Antibiotic						
Inactivation	0.00015199	0.00039363	0.00071370	0.00202682	0.00109269	0.00095104
Beta-Lactamase	0.00202187	0.00207459	0.00233121	0.00312114	0.00350872	0.00838457
Gene Modulating						
Resistance	0.00334187	0.00402040	0.00347039	0.00729531	0.00369716	0.0026973
Glycopeptide						
Resistance	0.00169378	0.00095572	0.00042634	0.00096721	0.00101164	0.00106289
MFS Transporter	0.00035602	0.0002760	0.00059566	0.00028770	0.00025541	0.00056180
Other	0	0.00017136	0.00021565	0.00029700	0	0.00014639
Other Efflux	0.00184142	0.00259964	0.00270195	0.0011482	0.00353145	0.00416624
Phosphotransferase	0.00159965	0.00114670	0.00180770	0.00256476	0.00243172	0.00263588
Quinolone						
Resistance	0.0005283	4.4988E-05	0.00013436	0.00061256	4.2786E-05	0.00014480
RND Antibiotic						
Efflux	0.00203728	0.00153476	0.00269370	0.00663792	0.00261980	0.0031307
rRNA						
Methyltransferase	0.00098909	0.00115772	0.00083807	0	0.00047581	0.00063200
Target Protection	0.0608950	0.04820264	0.03738186	0.01946760	0.03929105	0.02716019
unclassified	0.89746833	0.91547859	0.92565406	0.94532819	0.92155409	0.93044703
various	6.7554E-05	0	0	0	0.00012351	0.00012495

Table A9:**Abundance of antibiotic classes in protocol B2 using long gradient**

ANTIBIOTIC CLASS	FF3R1	GF2R1	BF2R3	EF3R2	AstR2	FstiR2
ABC Transporter	0.02398617	0.02225029	0.02441845	0.02362220	0.02445324	0.02036993
Acetyltransferase	0.00088774	0.00140345	0.00079236	0.00187002	0.00093287	0.00063931
Antibiotic						
Inactivation	0.000613	0.00083393	0.00135931	0.00061497	0.00136544	0.00101339
Beta-Lactamase	0.00121768	0.00125518	0.00138689	0.00264947	0.00240850	0.00638040
Gene Modulating						
Resistance	0.00496222	0.00513486	0.0033244	0.01359703	0.02607656	0.00207144
Glycopeptide						
Resistance	0.00302068	0.00507035	0.00183456	0.00208481	0.0042319	0.00215865
MFS Transporter	0.00043931	0.00038359	8.1709E-05	0.00051810	0.00011073	0.00065269
Other	7.8929E-05	0.00013991	0	0	0.00015083	0.0001006
Other Efflux	0.0047769	0.00293753	0.00260698	0.00686357	0.01382236	0.00385444

Phosphotransferase	0.00049566	0.00078929	0.00298858	0.00100317	0.00075528	0.00163148
Quinolone						
Resistance	8.3790E-05	0.00083076	0.00019847	0.00020901	0.00032704	6.1131E-05
RND Antibiotic						
Efflux	0.00211955	0.00156065	0.00307398	0.00511056	0.00257877	0.00284646
rRNA						
Methyltransferase	0.00064912	0.00047065	0.00014548	0.00118894	0.0007517	0.00089199
Target Protection	0.06000981	0.05059275	0.05548366	0.04686992	0.04049220	0.03991122
unclassified	0.89665874	0.90634673	0.90230504	0.8937981	0.88154240	0.91741671